

A Regional Stream Temperature Model for Assessing Climate Change Impacts on Thermal Habitat in Massachusetts

Prepared for

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Appendix A: Technical Memorandum – Literature Review

Appendix B: Technical Memorandum – Dataset Compilation and Review

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1 Introduction

Climate change poses a significant risk to native fish populations in Massachusetts (Farr et al., 2021; Galbraith, 2013). Coldwater species such as brown trout (*Salmo trutta*), brook trout (*Salvelinus fontinalis*) and other salmonids are particularly vulnerable to these changes. Warming air temperatures will lead to warmer waters, which increases the thermal stress on these species at multiple life stages, especially spawning (Mantua et al., 2010). In addition to rising air temperatures, climate change will also impact the hydrology of all rivers across the state through changes to the amount and frequency of precipitation leading to longer and more severe droughts as well as more extreme wet events both of which affect fish habitat availability. The survival of temperature-sensitive fish species depends on the availability of thermal habitats that are relatively resistant to changes in air temperature and precipitation. Identifying where these habitats are most likely to occur both now and in the future is critical to ensure that they can be preserved and protected.

Traditionally, identification of thermal habitats and climate refugia for coldwater fish species has focused primarily on the use of stream temperature data and/or models. Field-based surveys and data collection can be used to pinpoint locations that may be resistant to climate change (e.g., locations with high groundwater seepage); however, these methods are expensive and time-consuming, and ultimately limited in their spatial coverage. Stream temperature models are also commonly used to identify potential refugia by generating predictions in both gauged and un-gauged catchments over large regional areas (Gallice et al., 2015; Isaak et al., 2012; Siegel et al., 2023). However, the majority of existing temperature models are generally driven solely by air temperature (as well as other geospatial characteristics such as land use), and therefore do not reflect concurrent changes to precipitation-driven flow patterns. As a result, extended drought periods, which could further exacerbate higher water temperatures already caused by increasing air temperature, as well as the effects of extreme wet events are not always captured by these existing models.

Recent advances in machine learning modeling techniques (e.g., deep learning neural networks) have demonstrated new approaches to creating joint flow and temperature models that can respond to changes in both air temperature and precipitation (Jia et al., 2021; Sadler et al., 2022). Models such as these can be used to generate predictions of both flow and temperature along river networks. Other types of statistical and deterministic (i.e., process-based) models have also been used to simulate the combined effects of climate change on both flow and temperature, and the subsequent impacts on thermal habitats (Mantua et al., 2010; Van Vliet et al., 2013).

A literature review focusing on both conceptual models of the physical processes driving stream temperature variations as well as a review of various modeling frameworks and methodologies for understanding and predicting those processes is provided in Appendix A.

1.1 Study Objective

The primary objective of this project was to develop a joint flow and temperature model for predicting stream temperatures in gauged and ungauged streams and rivers across the state of Massachusetts under both current conditions and future climate change scenarios. The model predictions could then be used to project potential changes in thermal habitat due to climate-driven changes in both air temperature and precipitation (and resulting streamflow) patterns. The results of this study were intended to support subsequent data analyses and modeling efforts as well as resources management for identifying and prioritizing areas most likely to provide thermal habitats expected to be most resilient to climate change.

Following an initial review of the available data, it became clear that the amount of co-located flow and temperature monitoring data was not sufficient to support a joint flow and temperature model. Of the 1,206 continuous temperature stations and 181 flow stations originally identified, only 30 stations included more than one year of data with both parameters monitored simultaneously (Appendix B). However, to develop a model capable of making spatial predictions in ungauged streams across the state, a larger number of stations representing a greater diversity of landscape and hydro-morphologic conditions would be necessary. Therefore, the model ultimately developed for this project focuses solely on stream temperature; however, the methodology and modeling framework was designed to be readily extended to incorporate co-located flow and temperature data when it becomes available¹.

This project will also provide the basis for a regional flow and temperature modeling effort led by Dr. Jennifer Fair of the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). With funding from the Northeast Climate Adaptation Science Center (NECASC), the upcoming USGS project will build on the datasets, methods, models, and knowledge gained through this project to develop a new regional joint stream temperature and flow model to assess climate change impacts on thermal habitats across the northeast U.S. The transfer of data, models, and knowledge created by this project will be facilitated by myself as a co-Principal Investigator and MassWildlife as a project partner on the upcoming USGS project.

For this study, all analyses and modeling was performed using the R statistical programming language (R Core Team, 2023) with the {tidyverse} suite of data science packages (Wickham et al., 2019) along with the companion spatial extension packages (Pebesma & Bivand, 2023) and the {targets} package for data pipeline orchestration (Landau, 2021). The source code for this project is available at: <https://github.com/walkerjeffd/masswildlife-mastath>. The report and output dataset are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8145195>.

¹ The U.S. Geological Survey in collaboration with Walker Environmental Research and the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency is currently developing a new streamflow monitoring methodology and machine learning platform called the Flow Photo Explorer (FPE; <https://www.usgs.gov/apps/ecosheds/fpe/>). FPE uses deep learning models to estimate streamflow based on timelapse imagery. This method is designed to be a low-cost alternative to traditional streamflow gauging, specifically for use in headwater streams. When the next phase of FPE is complete, a large amount of new streamflow data will be available that will support future joint flow and temperature modeling efforts.

2 Data Sources

The first task in this project was to compile and review all available water temperature, streamflow, hydrography, landscape characteristics, and climate change projection datasets. A technical memorandum describing and comparing these datasets is provided in Appendix B. The following sub-sections focus on the specific data sources that were ultimately used for model development and predictions.

2.1 Temperature Monitoring Data

A database of continuous water temperature monitoring data was compiled from multiple sources (Table 1). Overall, the database included a total of 668,236 days of measurements collected at 1,108 stations by 20 agencies and organizations from 1994 to 2022. All together, these stations provided good spatial coverage across the state, with at least one station in every major basin except the Quinebaug bordering northeast Connecticut (Figure 1). A detailed summary of the available data as well as the process used to compile these datasets can be found in Appendix B.

2.2 Historical Air Temperature Data

Historical daily weather data was obtained from Daymet as a series of raster grids at a 1 km x 1 km spatial scale (Thornton et al., 2016). The data were retrieved as a set of tiles containing the minimum and maximum daily air temperature from 1994 to 2022. The tiles were spatially and temporally merged into multi-band rasters where each band contained the values for one date using the {terra} R package (Hijmans, 2023).

2.3 Hydrography and Spatial Attributes

The National Hydrography Dataset (NHD) Plus Version 2 (NHDPlusV2) was used as the geospatial framework for all models and analyses. NHDPlusV2 contains a medium resolution delineation of flowlines and catchments at approximately the 1:100,000 scale. Although other hydrography datasets with higher resolution are available (Appendix B), NHDPlusV2 was selected due to the availability of an enhanced routing network and associated attributes representing various basin characteristics including topography, geology, hydrology, and land use composition, among others (Schwarz & Wiczorek, 2018; Wiczorek et al., 2018). This database provides values of each attribute for both the local catchment of each flowline (stream reach), and for the entire drainage area upstream of each reach using a stream network accumulation algorithm. This dataset also includes land cover attributes computed within 50-m riparian buffers, which are useful as indicators of stream shading. The NHDPlusV2 flowlines layer was cropped to the Massachusetts state boundary, which for some basins resulted in only a portion of the river network being incorporated. However, because this study did not use a network-based modeling approach, the use of disconnected flowlines did not pose an issue.

Table 1: Summary of temperature monitoring stations by data provider.

Provider	Name	# Stations	# Days	Period	Source
CRWA	Charles River Watershed Assoc.	6	552	2022	CRWA
CTDEEP	CT Dept. of Energy and Environmental Protection	1	404	2010-2011	EcoSHEDS
HMF	Hopkins Memorial Forest	4	15,375	1994-2017	EcoSHEDS
HVA_BERKSHIRE	Housatonic Valley Association, Berkshires	17	1,908	2022	EcoSHEDS
MADEP	MA Dept. of Environmental Protection	534	20,491	2005-2010	EcoSHEDS
MAFW	MA Dept. of Fish and Wildlife	59	25,189	2005-2019	EcoSHEDS
MRWC	Miller's River Watershed Council	8	12,037	2013-2022	EcoSHEDS
NRWA	Nashua River Watershed Association	13	7,896	2020-2022	EcoSHEDS
OARS	Organization for the Assabet River	5	6,068	2012-2017	EcoSHEDS
PSU	Plymouth State University	3	2,388	2012-2014	EcoSHEDS
TU_DW	Trout Unlimited, Deerfield Watershed Chapter	9	2,780	2013-2022	EcoSHEDS
UMASS_USGS	Univ. of Massachusetts, USGS Cooperative Unit	185	253,972	2014-2022	EcoSHEDS
USFS	U.S. Forest Service	106	114,316	2010-2021	EcoSHEDS
USGS_Conte	U.S. Geological Survey, S.O. Conte Anadromous Fish Research Lab	70	76,039	1997-2022	EcoSHEDS
HOORWA	Hoosic River Watershed Association	18	1,647	2021-2022	HOORWA
HRF	Harvard Forest	4	18,454	2007-2022	HRF
IRWA	Ipswich River Watershed Association	18	1,588	2021-2022	IRWA
NEON	National Ecological Observatory Network	1	1,322	2019-2022	NEON
PIE-LTER	Plum Island Long Term Ecological Research Station	6	18,733	2001-2021	PIE-LTER
USGS	US Geological Survey	41	87,077	2007-2022	USGS-NWIS
TOTAL:		1,108	668,236	1994-2022	

Data Sources:

- CRWA: Lisa Kumpf (River Science & Restoration Program Manager), Pers. Comm. (Feb 13, 2023)
- EcoSHEDS: SHEDS Northeast Stream Temperature Database, <http://db.ecosheds.org/> (accessed Feb 1, 2023)
- HOORWA: <https://hoorwa.org/monitoring> (accessed Feb 24, 2023)
- HRF: Boose (2023) (accessed May 8, 2023)
- IRWA: Ryan O'Donnell (Programs Coordinator), Pers. Comm. (Mar 1, 2023)
- NEON: NEON (2023) (accessed May 8, 2023)
- PIE-LTER: <https://pie-lter.ecosystems.mbl.edu/data> (accessed Apr 26, 2023)
- USGS-NWIS: USGS (2023) (accessed Feb 13, 2023)

Figure 1: Map of temperature monitoring stations by data source.

2.4 Climate Change Projections

Climate projections of rising air temperatures were obtained from the Resilient MA Maps and Data Center² (MAEEA, 2023). These projections were created using a stochastic weather generator developed by Scott Steinschneider (Cornell University) as part of the MA Climate and Hydrologic Risk Project (Phase 1). The projections are based on downscaled Global Climate Models (GCMs) aggregated to the Hydrologic Unit Code (HUC) level 8 basins across the state. Projections are available for a baseline period (1950-2013) as well as two Representation Concentration Pathway (RCP) emissions scenarios (4.5 and 8.5). The RCP scenario projections are averaged over 30-year periods and provided for four time horizons centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, and 2090³. For each emissions scenario and time horizon, the projections include the annual and seasonal (winter, spring, summer, fall) changes in mean air temperature for each HUC8 basin. Because these projections were generated using a stochastic model, each projection includes the median as well as the 10th and 90th percentiles based on multiple simulated timeseries. The projected air temperature increases are relatively similar across the basins with median values ranging from 2 to 6 degC for RCP8.5 and 1.5 to 3 degC for RCP 4.5 (Figure 2). Because the RCP 4.5 scenario is becoming increasingly unlikely as emissions continue to rise worldwide, the water temperature projections generated in this study focus exclusively on the RCP 8.5 scenario.

Figure 2: Projected air temperature increases by HUC8 basin under RCP4.5 and 8.5 emissions scenarios.

Data from (MA EEA, 2023).

² <https://resilientma-mapcenter-mass-eoea.hub.arcgis.com/>

³ Projections for 2090 are averaged over a 20-year period (2080-2100)

2.5 Thermal Classifications

A series of thermal threshold developed by Beauchene et al. (2014) was used to classify each stream reach based on mean July water temperature (Table 2). That study also includes two alternative sets of thresholds based on 1) the June – August mean water temperature, and 2) the maximum daily mean temperature. However, the thresholds based on July temperatures were best suited for the models and datasets used in this study.

Table 2: Thermal classification thresholds from Beauchene et al. (2014)

Thermal Class	Mean July Water Temp. (°C)
Cold	< 18.45
Cool	18.45 – 22.30
Warm	> 22.30

3 Data Processing

Before developing the models, the following data processing tasks were performed to review, clean, and prepare the various datasets to be used by those models.

3.1 Station Georeferencing

The temperature monitoring stations (Section 2.1) were georeferenced to the NHDPlusV2 flowlines in order to relate the location of each station along the stream network. Each station was snapped to the nearest flowline using the `{sf}` R package (Pebesma, 2018; Pebesma & Bivand, 2023). Flowline snapping was limited to a maximum distance of 100 m. Stations that exceeded this distance from the nearest flowline were assumed to be located on smaller streams not included in the NHDPlusV2 delineation or located within wetlands or other large water bodies that were not free-flowing, and thus were excluded from model development.

3.2 Basin Delineation

The drainage area of each station was delineated using USGS StreamStats (Newson, 2018). Although each station was also georeferenced to a specific NHDPlusV2 flowline, the NHDPlusV2 dataset does not include polygons representing the complete drainage area to each flowline. Furthermore, although NHDPlusV2 includes the individual catchments of each flowline, accumulating those catchments along the stream network to determine the total drainage area for each point is not trivial. Due to the complexity of that task, the USGS StreamStats tool was used instead to automatically delineate the drainage basin for each monitoring station.

3.3 Temperature Data Processing

For each temperature station, the raw data were reviewed and processed using the following steps:

1. **Daily Temperature Aggregation:** compute the daily minimum, mean, and maximum temperatures from the instantaneous measurements (i.e., 15-minute or hourly), except when daily values were already available (e.g., USGS NWIS stations).
2. **Temperature Data QAQC:** the temperature monitoring data was reviewed based on standard QAQC checks (e.g., valid ranges, spike detection, maximum daily changes), and erroneous or abnormal data removed from the dataset.
3. **Station Screening:** stations that met any of the following criteria were excluded:
 - a. Located within a waterbody that is 1 km² or larger or within 100 m of the shoreline to exclude stations within lakes, ponds, or reservoirs. A few stations were exempted from these criteria as they were located at the outlet of tributaries flowing into a waterbody.
 - b. Located within 100 m of a dam based on the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) National Inventory of Dams (NID) database accessed via the {dams} R package (Goteti & Stachelek, 2020; U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 2023).
 - c. Located on a large river with a drainage area of 10,000 km² or more (e.g., Connecticut or Merrimack Rivers).

Following these procedures, total number of stations was reduced from 1,108 to 955. Following these procedures, the resulting daily mean temperatures showed a strong seasonal pattern (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Seasonal pattern of all daily mean water temperatures following data QAQC and station screening.
Black dot = daily mean temperature value at a single station. Blue line = Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing (LOESS) line.

3.4 Basin-wide Air Temperatures

For each station, a timeseries of basin-wide mean daily air temperatures were computed over the period of record, 1994 – 2022. These timeseries were generated using the {exactextractr} R package (Baston, 2022) to intersect the drainage basins delineated using USGS StreamStats (Section 3.2) with the gridded Daymet tiles containing historical daily minimum and maximum air temperature (Section 2.2). Daily mean air temperature was then calculated as the mean of the minimum and maximum air temperatures on each day.

4 Stream Temperature Model

This study uses the following multi-step modeling approach:

1. For each temperature station, fit a non-linear air-water temperature model to weekly air and water temperature data (Mohseni et al., 1998). The parameters of this model are then used to indicate the relative sensitivity of water temperature to changes in air temperature (i.e., thermal sensitivity, see Section 4.1 for detailed description of these parameters).
2. Use the full set of estimated air-water temperature models from step 1 to develop a multiple regression model for predicting those parameters based on spatial basin characteristics.
3. Use the spatial model from step 2 to estimate the air-water temperature model parameters for each stream reach across the state.
4. For each stream reach, use the estimated parameters from step 3 to predict weekly water temperatures based on historical air temperatures (see rationale in Section 4.1 below for using weekly instead of daily temperatures).
5. Repeat step 4 for a series of climate change scenarios representing a range of rising air temperatures.

This methodology is based on three other stream temperature modeling studies:

- Kelleher et al. (2012) estimated the primary drivers of thermal sensitivity using data from 57 stations in Pennsylvania. For each station, the thermal sensitivity was represented as the estimated slope (E) of a linear air-water temperature model fit to each station. They then fit a multiple linear regression model to estimate those thermal sensitivities (slopes) based on spatial characteristics (e.g., channel size, solar radiation, stream order, baseflow index, elevation, etc.). The results showed that in small streams, baseflow (BFI) was the major determinant of thermal sensitivity, while stream order was most important in larger streams.
- Mayer (2012) also used a regional multiple linear regression model to identify the primary landscape and stream metrics that drive variability in summer stream temperatures and thermal sensitivities at 104 stations across the Pacific Northwest. The most important factors were baseflow index, which represents groundwater discharge, and the stream channel slope.

- Segura et al. (2015) used a similar methodology to identify the primary drivers of air-water temperature relationships using the USGS GAGES II database at 171 sites across the US. Although they also applied the non-linear air-water temperature model by Mohseni et al. (1998) at each site, they instead fit a multiple linear regression model to predict the intercept and slope of a linear air-water based on climatic, hydrologic and land cover attributes. Comparisons between the linear and nonlinear air-water temperature models showed similar performance (R^2 of 0.94 and 0.96, respectively) and thus they simpler linear model was used for the subsequent regional model. They also evaluated the seasonal hysteresis of air-water temperature relationships and found drainage area was a major control on thermal sensitivity, while groundwater effects were most evident in spring and fall (although they were still significant in all seasons).

These three previous studies focused on identifying the primary drivers of spatial variations in stream temperature and thermal sensitivity. For this study, a new methodology was developed using gradient boosted decision trees (XGBoost) to not only identify those primary drivers, but also to predict stream temperatures at ungauged stream reaches under both historical baseline conditions and future climate change projections.

4.1 Air-Water Temperature Model

One of the most widely used stream temperature models is the nonlinear regression model originally developed by Mohseni et al. (1998). This model represents the relationship between weekly mean air and water temperatures using an S-shaped logistic curve defined by the following equation:

$$T_w = \mu - \frac{\alpha - \mu}{1 + \exp(\gamma(\beta - T_a))}$$

where T_w is the weekly mean water temperature (degC), μ is the lower bound (minimum) water temperature (degC), α is the upper bound (maximum) water temperature (degC), β is the air temperature at the inflection point (degC), and γ is a measure of the maximum curve slope (degC / degC) at the inflection point.

To help develop an intuitive sense of these parameters, an interactive data visualization⁴ of this model was created (Figure 4). By changing each parameter, the reader can get a feel for how the shape of the curve changes as the value is increased or decreased. The resulting intuition is useful when interpreting the model results below.

⁴ <https://observablehq.com/@walkerenvres/air-water-temperature-model>

Figure 4: Screenshot of the interactive data visualization for the Mohseni et al. (1998) air-water temperature model.

Available online at <https://observablehq.com/@walkerenvres/air-water-temperature-model>

The parameters of this model can be used to understand various physical dynamics related to the air-water temperature dynamics at a given location (Mohseni & Stefan, 1999). The upper bound parameter, α , defines the maximum water temperature that can occur for any given air temperature. The S-shaped curve causes the water temperature to asymptotically approach this upper bound as air temperatures rise to high values. The threshold behavior of water temperatures is due to evaporative heat loss from the stream channel. The non-linearity of this relationship is an important dynamic to capture when using any stream temperature model, especially for generating climate change predictions. Linear models would not account for the greater importance of evaporative heat loss at higher air temperatures, and would therefore generate unrealistic predictions when extrapolated to higher air temperatures (Mohseni & Stefan, 1999).

The air-water temperature model can also indicate groundwater influence through both the slope (γ) and lower bound (μ) parameters. Groundwater discharge can have a buffering effect on water temperature, especially in headwater streams where groundwater may represent a significant portion of the total heat flux into the channel (Poole & Berman, 2001). This buffering effect changes the S-shape logistic curve by 1) raising the lower bound (μ) due reflecting relatively warm water temperatures > 0 degC during winter, and 2) reducing the slope of the curve (γ) reflecting less thermal sensitivity as changes in air temperature are buffered by a relatively constant heat influx from groundwater (Figure 5). Similar buffering effects can also be caused by thermal discharges or reservoir releases.

Figure 5: Conceptual linear and non-linear relationships between water and air temperature of groundwater and non-groundwater streams.

Extracted from Caissie (2006).

The non-linear model by Mohseni et al. (1998) has been widely used to understand the drivers of spatial and temporal variability in air-water temperature relationships (see Appendix A). There are a number of modifications to the original model designed to improve its performance for using daily data by incorporating other driving variables such as flow. Piotrowski & Napiorkowski (2019) provides a relatively recent review and comparison of the various modifications to the original model along with a summary of the applications of this model from different studies.

Two important considerations when using the Mohseni et al. (1998) model are:

1. This model does not incorporate the lagged effect of air temperature changes on water temperature, which can be important for estimating daily temperatures (Letcher et al., 2016). Therefore, the model is best applied to weekly mean temperatures in order to reduce the effect of that lag, which is often less than 7 days long.
2. Fitting the model parameters to observed data can be challenging due to the hysteresis of air-water temperature relationships. Hysteresis is another consequence of the lagged air temperature effect and causes the air-water temperature relationship to shift seasonally, especially between the first half of the year when air temperatures are warming, and the second half when temperatures are cooling. The common approach to address this hysteresis is to fit two separate models – one for the warming period, and another for the cooling period – as was done in the original development of this model (Mohseni et al., 1998).

4.1.1 Input Dataset

For each temperature monitoring station, an input dataset was created by pairing daily mean water temperatures (Section 3.3) with the basin-wide air temperatures computed using Daymet data (Section 3.4). The daily air and water temperatures were then aggregated to weekly values based on the number of days from the start of each year (week 1 = Jan 1 – 7, week 2 = Jan 8 – 14, etc.). Incomplete weekly values based on fewer than 7 days of data were removed.

The stations were then filtered based on the total number of weekly values at each station, and the seasonal distribution of those values to ensure the dataset for each station included a sufficient range of temperature conditions. For example, fitting the non-linear air-water temperature model to data collected only in summer (or only in winter) would be problematic as the range of the data would be insufficient to estimate the full set of model parameters.

To identify the minimum number of weekly values for each station, the range of all values at each station (difference between the maximum and minimum weekly mean temperatures) were compared against the total number of weekly values. A threshold of 25 weeks was selected as the range in weekly values tended to be much smaller for stations with less data compared to those with more data (Figure 6).

The percent of weekly temperatures during the summer season was then used as a secondary criterion to ensure that each station included a fair representation of high summer temperatures, but also included at least some cooler non-summer temperatures. The summer period was defined based on the distributions of weekly temperatures, which tended to be highest between weeks 18 and 43 (April 30 – October 28) (Figure 7). Using this range of summer weeks, the fraction of all weekly values during the summer was calculated for each station (excluding those with less than 25 weeks of data). Compared to the total number of weekly values, the fraction of summer weeks was more variable among stations with less data, and then converged towards a mean of approximately 50% for stations with more than 300 weeks of data (5+ years). An acceptable range of 30 – 80% was chosen to exclude stations with too much or too little summer data, and to allow for stations that primarily contained summer data as that is the primary season of interest for this study.

Figure 6: Range of weekly mean temperature values at each station compared to the total number of weeks of data.
Red vertical line indicates minimum threshold of 25 weeks of data. Stations with more than 200 weeks of data are not shown.

Figure 7: Distributions of weekly mean temperatures by week of the year.
Shaded region shows selected summer season between weeks 18 and 43 (April 30 – October 28). Excludes stations with fewer than 25 weeks of data.

Figure 8: Fraction of weekly values during summer compared to total number of weekly values at each station.
Excludes stations with less than 25 weeks of data. Shaded region indicates allowable range of weekly summer fractions (30–80%).

Of the 955 initial stations, only 357 (37%) remained for model fitting after 598 (63%) stations were excluded based on the following three criteria (Figure 9):

1. at least 25 complete weekly mean values,
2. at least 30% of weekly values during summer (April 30 – October 28), and
3. no more than 80% of weekly values during summer.

Of the 598 excluded stations, the majority (60%) were stations monitored by MA Dept. of Environmental Protection on an annual rotating schedule such that each station contained less than one year of data.

The weekly water and air temperatures of the remaining 357 stations exhibit the expected non-linear S-shape of the logistic function (Figure 10). At high air temperatures (> 20 degC), the upper end of the S-shape curve is not as apparent as at the lower air temperatures (< 5 degC) due to the variability across stations – stations with larger drainage areas tended to have steeper curves that reach higher maximum water temperatures than those with smaller drainage areas.

Figure 9: Maps showing stations that passed or failed screening criteria based on weekly values.

Figure 10: Relationship between weekly water and air temperature across all stations meeting screening criteria.
Points colored by drainage area of the delineated basins from USGS StreamStats.

4.1.2 Model Fitting

For each temperature station, the non-linear logistic model by Mohseni et al. (1998) was fit to the weekly water and air temperatures (Section 4.1.1) using the `nls()` non-linear least squares

routine in R (R Core Team, 2023). Model statistics, parameter estimates, predictions and residuals were generated using the {broom} R package (Robinson et al., 2023). Additional model goodness-of-fit statistics such as the Nash-Sutcliffe Efficient (NSE) were computed using the {hydroGOF} R package (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2020).

For each station, two versions of the logistic temperature model (LOM) were initially fit:

- **LOM4** – the complete model where all 4 parameters ($\mu, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$) are estimated from the data (see equation in Section 4.1 above)
- **LOM3** – a simplified 3-parameter version of the model with the lower bound parameter set to 0 degC ($\mu = 0$), and the remaining three parameters (α, β, γ) then estimated from the data.

The simplified 3-parameter version of the model (LOM3) has been used in other studies (Caldwell et al., 2015; Segura et al., 2015). By setting the $\mu = 0$, this version of the model assumes water temperatures will asymptotically approach 0 degC as air temperatures fall below freezing. Effectively, this version of the model constrains the estimated water temperatures to non-negative values. This constraint introduces the limitation that it cannot represent situations where the true lower bound, $\mu > 0$. For example, a large thermal release or high groundwater discharge can cause water temperatures to be relatively warm even when air temperatures are below freezing (Mohseni & Stefan, 1999; Poole & Berman, 2001). However, the plot of the weekly water and air temperature data across all sites showed that none of the stations exhibit such behavior as water temperatures gradually approach 0 degC with decreasing air temperature (Figure 10).

4.1.3 Model Performance

The goodness-of-fit of the each model across all stations were evaluated using a series of model performance and error statistics computed with the {hydroGOF} R package (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2020):

- **ME**: mean error (degC)
- **MAE**: mean absolute error (≥ 0 , degC)
- **R²**: Coefficient of determination (0 to 1)
- **RMSE**: Root mean square error (≥ 0 , degC)
- **NSE**: Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (≤ 1), which reflects the relative amount of residual variance (noise) to total variance in the data (information) (Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970)
- **KGE**: Kling-Gupta Efficiency (≤ 1), which incorporates three separate components of model accuracy: correlation, bias and variability (Gupta et al., 2009)

The NSE and KGE metrics are commonly used in hydrologic modeling (Knoben et al., 2019). Although the two have similar ranges from -Infinity to 1, they require different interpretations. For example, NSE values between 0 and 1 indicate the model performs better than using a simple mean of the data, with a value of 1 indicating perfect prediction accuracy. However, for

KGE, a comparable comparison relative to the mean of the data occurs at $1 - \sqrt{2} = 0.41$ (Knoben et al., 2019). Although KGE and NSE cannot be easily compared to each other, they can each provide a useful basis for comparing between models.

The distributions of each model goodness-of-fit metric showed similar performance between the LOM3 and LOM4 models with the exception of the KGE metric, which showed better performance for the LOM4 model for which the lower bound (μ) was estimated from the data (Figure 11). However, the KGE and NSE values for the LOM3 model were both relatively high (> 98% of stations had both KGE and NSE > 0.9). Similarly, the goodness of fit metrics were relatively similar between the two models when computed over all values and stations together as a measure of global model performance (Table 3).

In addition to the similar goodness-of-fit metrics, the model residuals were also similar between the two models, especially at medium-to-high temperatures (Figure 12). Although the residual patterns differed somewhat between the two models at lower temperatures, these differences are less relevant than the residuals at higher temperatures as the goal of this model is to generate predictions during the summer in order to classify thermal habitats. The differences in residuals at low temperatures is expected as the only difference between the LOM3 and LOM4 models is the value of the lower bound parameter (μ), which controls the minimum predicted water temperature and was set to zero in LOM3.

Figure 11: Distributions of model performance metrics across all stations using the LOM3 and LOM4 models.

Violin shapes are similar to boxplots but provide a more continuous representation of data density (Hintze & Nelson, 1998). Middle line indicates median value.

Table 3: Goodness-of-fit metrics for LOM3 and LOM4 based on all data and stations.

	LOM3	LOM4
# Stations	355	355
# Values	69,301	69,301
ME	0.057	0.000
MAE	0.988	0.939
RMSE	1.29	1.25
R²	0.971	0.973
NSE	0.971	0.973
KGE	0.970	0.980

Figure 12: Model residuals compared to predicted values at all stations using LOM3 and LOM4.

4.1.4 Estimated Coefficients

Despite having similar model performance metrics, the two models differed in the distributions of the estimated values for some parameters, especially for the slope parameter (γ) (Figure 13). Pairwise scatterplots of the parameters estimated using LOM4 show that the slope parameter (γ) was highly (though non-linearly) correlated with the lower bound parameter (μ) (Pearson correlation coefficient, $r = 0.75$). The upper bound parameter (α) was also negatively correlated with the lower bound (μ) ($r = -0.72$) based on LOM4. For LOM3, all three parameters were moderately correlated with correlation coefficients of 0.52, -0.63, and -0.41 for (α, β), (α, γ), and (β, γ), respectively.

Figure 13: Pairwise comparisons between estimated coefficients using LOM3 and LOM4 models.
 This figure was generated using the `ggpairs()` function from the `{GGally}` R package (Schloerke et al., 2021). Red indicates LOM3 model, blue indicates LOM4. Note that no values of μ are shown for LOM3, since it was set to zero for that version of the model.

Using the estimated parameters for each model, the predicted air-water temperature curves were relatively similar between the two models, except for at low air temperatures where there was more variability in the LOM4 curves (Figure 14). At intermediate air temperatures (approx. 5 to 15 degC), the curves for both models have a relatively small range in predicted water temperatures (roughly 3 to 5 degC). However, at high air temperatures (> 15 degC), the range of predictions increases to over 10 degC. The prediction curves from both models also reflect the variability in the water temperatures across the stations when air temperatures are high.

The variability of these curves (especially at high air temperatures) can be used as an indicator of thermal sensitivity. Stations where the fitted curve predicts relatively cool water temperatures for a given air temperature are indicative of stream reaches most likely provide cold water habitat. Because of the simplicity of this model, the shapes of these curves are defined by only a few parameters. In the next step of the project, a second model was developed to estimate these parameters based on geospatial characteristics such as topography, land use, drainage area, etc.

Due to the similarity in performance and predictions between the two models, as well as the high correlation between the lower bound (μ) and slope (γ) parameters using LOM4, the simpler LOM3 model was chosen for all subsequent analyses.

Figure 14: Predicted air-water temperature curves at all sites for LOM3 and LOM4.

Each line is the estimated air-water temperature curve for a single station. The black points show observed values from all stations and are the same for both models.

4.2 Regional Model

After fitting the air-water temperature model to each station, a regional model was developed to estimate the parameters of that model for each stream reach (excluding large rivers) across the state. The estimated air-water temperature curves were then used to classify reaches based on thermal habitat criteria, and to evaluate changes in predicted water temperature and habitat classification under future climate change scenarios. As discussed at the end of the last section, the following spatial model was developed using the estimated parameters from the 3-parameter version of the air-temperature water model (LOM3) as it performed sufficiently and its results were very similar to the original 4-parameter model (LOM4).

This modeling approach was inspired by a few earlier studies that developed regional models to estimate the parameters of the air-water temperature curve based on spatial variables (see Section 4) (Kelleher et al., 2012; Mayer, 2012; Segura et al., 2015). All three of those studies used stepwise multiple linear regression for developing a regional model to identify the primary drivers of spatial variations in stream temperature and thermal sensitivity. For this study, the goal was to not only identify those drivers, but also make predictions for all ungauged streams across the state. A variety of modeling techniques and frameworks were considered including multiple linear regression, k-nearest neighbors, random forests, and neural networks, among other classic statistical and machine learning algorithms. Ultimately, boosted gradient decision trees were selected as the framework for developing this regional model due to their flexibility in representing complex variable relationships and ability to achieve high predictive power.

Boosted gradient decision trees belong to the Classification And Regression Tree (CART) class of machine learning algorithms (Appling et al., 2022). CART algorithms are useful for modeling

complex, non-linear, and multivariate relationships between variables. They are often preferred for tasks where the goal is more to make accurate predictions than to develop a better understanding of the underlying drivers and dynamics within a model (Shmueli, 2010).

Boosted trees use an ensemble-learning approach whereby a random set of decision trees are first generated and then the predictions of those trees combined to generate one single estimate (Chen & Guestrin, 2016; Feigl et al., 2021). Boosted tree algorithms differ from bagged tree algorithms, which are another form of decision tree models, in that the ensemble members of a boosted tree are iteratively trained and then added to the ensemble sequentially, whereas bagged tree algorithms train all members of the ensemble in parallel. In other words, boosted tree algorithms create complementary trees, while bagged algorithms simply average across multiple individual trees (Souaissi et al., 2023). XGBoost is a specific implementation of boosted decision trees designed to increase the efficiency and scalability of previous boosted tree algorithms as well as reduce overfitting.

Used in a variety of stream temperature studies, XGBoost is often found to be one of the top performing models. Feigl et al. (2021) compared six machine learning models (linear regression, random forest, XGBoost, feed forward neural networks (FNN), and two kinds of recurrent neural networks (RNNs)) to predict daily water temperatures at 10 basins in Austria. They found mixed results with XGBoost and FNN performing best in 4 of the 10 catchments, and RNNs performing best in the largest catchments. Similarly, Weierbach et al. (2022) compared two machine learning algorithms (support vector machines (SVM), XGBoost) against a baseline multiple regression model for predicting monthly stream temperatures in the Mid-Atlantic and Pacific Northwest. The XGBoost model outperformed both the regression and SVM models in predicting monthly temperatures at ungauged basins (average RMSE = 0.64, 0.99, and 1.30 degC, respectively). Lastly, Souaissi et al. (2023) compared XGBoost against random forest, multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS), and generalized additive models (GAMs) for regional estimates of maximum water temperatures. Their results showed that the MARS and GAMs outperformed both the RF and XGBoost algorithms; however, they note that this may be related to the relatively small observation dataset that was used and included only 24 stations.

Due to its predictive power, flexibility in representing complex, non-linear relationships, and its ability to handle different types and distributions (i.e., non-normal) among the input variables, the XGBoost algorithm was chosen for developing a region model to estimate the air-water temperature curve parameters at both gauged and ungauged stream reaches across Massachusetts.

4.2.1 Input Dataset

The input dataset for the regional model was comprised of the estimated parameter values for the fitted LOM3 air-water temperature model along with a set of spatial variables from the NHDPlusV2 attributes datasets (Section 2.3) (Wieczorek et al., 2018).

Maps showing the estimated parameter values at each station did not reveal any major spatial patterns (Figure 15), with the exception of the upper bound parameter (α), which tended to be

somewhat higher in the western part of the state. There were no other major spatial patterns for the inflection point (β) or slope (γ) parameters identified.

Figure 15: Maps of estimated air-water temperature model parameters (LOM3) at each station.

The estimated parameters values at temperature station were merged with the NHDPlusV2 attributes for the nearest flowline identified during the station georeferencing process (Section 3.1). Only the total cumulative value of each attribute (i.e., basin-wide mean value) was included in the dataset. The local catchment values were not used but could be considered in future updates to this model. A total of 44 attributes representing the topography, land use, and number/size of upstream impoundments were ultimately used as predictors for the XGBoost model.

4.2.2 Model Fitting

Separate regional models were fit to estimates of the three air-water temperature model parameters (α , β , γ ; see Section 4.1) based on the same set of spatial attributes. Each model was built using the {xgboost} R package (Chen et al., 2023) along with the {tidymodels} framework for modeling and machine learning in R (Kuhn & Wickham, 2020). To train each model and prevent over-fitting, the input dataset was first split into separate training (75%) and testing (25%) subsets. The training dataset was then repeatedly split using 10-fold cross-validation for tuning the hyperparameters of each model.

Hyperparameters are algorithmic parameters that govern the structure and learning process of a machine learning model. These differ from the model parameters that are used to generate predictions. Many machine learning models, especially those within the CART class of algorithms, require that hyperparameters be carefully tuned to avoid overfitting. The

hyperparameters for the XGBoost model include the number of trees in each ensemble, the tree depth, the minimum number of data points for a node to be split, a loss reduction factor, the number of predictors that are sampled at each tree split, the sample size exposed to the fitting routine, and the learning rate (Table 4). These hyperparameters were tuned using grid of size 100, where each row of the grid contains a unique set of values generated by a latin hypercube.

Table 4: XGBoost hyperparameter tuning ranges and results

Hyperparameter	Description	Tuning Range	Final Tuned Values		
			α Model	β Model	γ Model
trees	# Trees	1 – 2000	434	1,130	1,888
tree_depth	Tree depth	1 – 15	14	5	7
min_n	Min. data points for node split	2 – 40	6	9	15
loss_reduction	Loss reduction factor	1e-10 – 1e-1.5	5.16e-2	1.20e-8	3.87e-4
sample_size	Sample size for fitting	0.1 – 1	0.818	0.601	0.765
mtry	# predictors sampled at each split	1 – 46	10	30	40
learn_rate	Learning rate	1e-4 – 1e-2	1.81e-2	4.84e-3	8.50e-3

For each set of hyperparameter values, the model was fit to each of the training splits in the 10-fold cross-validation dataset. The accuracy of each model was then assessed by computing the root mean square error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) on each training split. The performance metrics were then averaged over all 10 folds of the cross-validation dataset yielding the mean RMSE and R^2 of each set of hyperparameter values based only on the test (hold-out) splits of each fold. Relationships between the mean RMSE and R^2 values and each hyperparameter revealed that the learning rate and loss reduction factor were the two most important parameters and had the largest effect on model accuracy. The set of hyperparameters with the lowest mean RMSE was then used for training the final model (Table 4).

After tuning the hyperparameters for each model, the final model was fit using the complete training dataset from the initial split. Performance of the final model was then assessed using the testing dataset from that same split, which had been held out from the hyperparameter tuning process. Performance of each model was relatively similar between the training and testing splits for the upper bound (α) model, but less so for the inflection point (β) and slope (γ) models. However, scatterplots of observed⁵ vs. predicted values showed that prediction accuracy of the test splits were not substantially different from the training split. Overall, these results suggest the models may suffer slightly from overfitting but are capable of generating reasonably accurate estimates of all three parameters. Furthermore, the best performing model – the upper bound (α) parameter model – is also the most important of the three due to its large effect on the shape of the air-water temperature curve. Changes in the upper bound (α) led to the largest change in estimated water temperatures (compared to β and γ) when air

⁵ For the regional model, “observed values” refers to the estimated values of each parameter from the LOM3 air-water temperature model.

temperatures are relatively high. Lastly, further validation of the predicted weekly water temperatures at each site using the estimated parameter values for the air-water temperature curve generated by the regional model showed nearly identical model performance between the training and testing subsets confirming that the models are not overfit (see next section).

Table 5: Goodness-of-fit statistics for final regional models based on training and testing datasets.

ME = Mean Error, MAE = Mean Absolute Error, RMSE = Root Mean Square Error, R² = Coefficient of Determination

	α Model		β Model		γ Model	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
# Values	266	89	266	89	266	89
ME	-0.014	-0.14	-0.17	-0.13	0.000020	-0.0013
MAE	0.59	1.22	0.51	0.63	0.0060	0.011
RMSE	0.95	1.72	0.78	0.90	0.0085	0.017
R ²	0.92	0.76	0.67	0.35	0.86	0.29

Figure 16: Scatterplots of observed and predicted values for each air-temperature curve parameter based the final fitted model applied each training and testing dataset.

Dotted black line indicates 1:1 line of equality. Solid black line is a linear regression model fit each set of data points.

4.2.3 Combined Model Validation

As an additional validation step, the air-water temperature curve parameters estimated by the final XGBoost models were used to predict weekly water temperatures at each of the monitoring stations and compared to observed data. This validation evaluated the accuracy of both models when they are combined in the two-step process that was later used to estimate stream temperatures of ungauged streams. Comparison of the four primary model performance

metrics (see Section 4.1.3 for definitions) showed virtually no difference in model accuracy between the training and testing datasets (Figure 17). The overall error statistics also show similar performance with $R^2 = 0.97$, $RMSE = 1.3 \text{ degC}$, and $NSE = 0.97$ for both datasets (Table 6: Goodness-of-fit metrics of the regional training and testing datasets based on predicted and observed weekly water temperatures.), which are nearly identical to the performance metrics for the air-water temperature model itself (Table 3). Lastly, scatterplots of the observed and predicted weekly mean temperatures using the estimated temperature curves also suggest the model does not generate biased predictions nor suffer from overfitting (Figure 18).

This validation demonstrates that when combined, the two models achieve high predictive performance, even at ungauged stream reaches. Throughout this section, the testing dataset included stations that were held out from the dataset used to train the regional model. Therefore, the accuracies of both the estimated air-water temperature parameters themselves as well as the subsequent weekly mean temperature predictions at these stations indicates the ability of this combined model to predict water temperatures at ungauged stream reaches.

Figure 17: Distributions of model performance metrics for predicting weekly water temperatures at each station using the estimated air-water temperature curve parameters from the regional model.
“Train” and “Test” refer to the dataset split used to fit the regional model. Parameters estimated at stations within the Test subset were not used for model fitting and represent an independent dataset for validation.

Table 6: Goodness-of-fit metrics of the regional training and testing datasets based on predicted and observed weekly water temperatures.

Predictions were computed using the estimated parameters for the air-water temperature curves as generated by the regional model.

	Training	Testing
# Stations	266	89
# Values	52,777	16,524
ME	0.059	0.052
MAE	0.994	0.969
R ²	0.971	0.971
RMSE	1.301	1.260
NSE	0.971	0.971
KGE	0.970	0.971

Figure 18: Comparison of observed and predicted weekly mean water temperature using the estimated air-water temperature curve parameters from the regional model.

Train and test refer to the dataset split performed for fitting the regional model.

4.2.4 Variable Importance

Using the final fitted regional models, the primary drivers of each parameter were identified by computing variable importance scores with the {vip} R package (Greenwell & Boehmke, 2020). The upper bound (α) model was driven primarily by the fractions of both tree canopy and forest cover within 50 m riparian buffer, the total stream length and basin area, the total normal and maximum impoundment storage volumes, and the fraction of open water. These results are consistent with the conceptual model that stream temperatures can be controlled by riparian shading and be heavily influenced by upstream impoundments. The primary drivers of the inflection point (β) model, however, included different variables such as the amount of barren land use within the riparian buffer, the minimum basin elevation, agricultural and wetland land use, and total stream length. Lastly, the slope (γ) model was heavily influenced by the total open development land use within the riparian corridor, drainage area, baseflow index, and total wetlands cover.

Figure 19: Variable importance plots for the final fitted version of each regional XGBoost model.

4.2.5 Estimated Spatial Parameters

The three fitted regional models were used to estimate the parameters of the air-water temperature curve for each stream reach across the state using the select attributes dataset for NHDPlusV2 flowlines (Section 2.3). Larger rivers with drainage areas greater than 10,000 km² were excluded from these predictions as they are not the focus of this study and often have different dynamics than smaller rivers.

Maps of the estimated parameters reveal some spatial patterns in the air-temperature dynamics (Figure 15). The upper bound (α) parameter tended to have lower estimates (< 20 degC) in the western half of the state indicating that streams tend to be cooler, even under high air temperature due to the non-linear S-shape of the temperature curve. The other two parameters (β , γ) did not show any major state-wide patterns, but do reveal some areas where a relatively large number of reaches had consistently high (or low) estimates. For example, the slope parameter (γ) was relatively high in the upper reaches of the Westfield and Housatonic basins.

param : α

param : β

param : γ

Figure 20: Estimated air-water temperature curve parameters using regional model.

4.3 Water Temperature Predictions

The estimated air-water temperature curves were used to predict monthly water temperatures using 30-yr (1971-2000) normal monthly air temperatures from PRISM (PRISM Climate Group, 2023; Wieczorek et al., 2019). Historical weekly air temperatures could also be computed using the daily Daymet gridded datasets (Section 2.2). However, doing so would require significant computation resources as the drainage area for each of the 10,000+ NHDPlusV2 flowlines would need to be delineated, intersected with the Daymet grids, and then spatially averaged.

Therefore, the pre-computed values from PRISM were used instead of the daily Daymet data to generate spatial predictions of mean monthly water temperatures for the 30-yr normal period (1971-2000). Using the predicted mean July air temperature for the 30-yr normal period, the thermal class of each reach was then assigned using the thresholds by (Beauchene et al., 2014) (Section 2.5).

Maps of the predicted July water temperatures and resulting thermal classes show a strong spatial gradient across the state (Figure 21). The total number of river miles for each thermal class also shows differences across the major basins in the state⁶ (Figure 22). Cooler temperatures occur more often in the Western part of the state, especially in the Middle Hudson, Deerfield, Hudson-Hoosic, and Shetucket basins⁷. Higher temperatures tend to occur in the eastern and coastal regions such as the Piscataqua-Salmon Falls, Cape Cod, Charles River, Narragansett Bay basins. As expected, the vast majority of river miles classified as Cold (82%) were found in first order streams followed by 14% in second order streams and the remaining 4% in third, fourth, and fifth order streams (Figure 23a). Over 40% of first order river miles were classified as Cold, followed by 57% as Cool, and < 2% as Warm (Figure 23b). First order streams were also the most abundant, comprising 60% of the total river miles (7,762 km) among all stream orders followed by second order streams that make up 20%.

⁶ Each basin only includes flowlines within the MA state boundary and thus the distributions for some basins are based on a relatively small number of stream reaches. For example, the Shetucket, Piscataqua-Salmon Falls, and Middle Hudson basins each cover less than 100 km² in MA, which is a small percentage of their total areas.

⁷ Only a small fraction of the Middle Hudson and Shetucket basins are found within the MA state boundary, and thus these results may be biased towards low-order headwater streams located at the edge of each basin.

a) Predicted July Water Temp.

b) Thermal Classification

Figure 21: Predicted July mean water temperature and thermal classifications based on 30-yr (1971-2000) normal air temperature.

Figure 22: Distribution of thermal classes by basin based on 30-yr (1971-2000) normal air temperature.

Note: each basin only includes flowlines within the MA state boundary and thus the distributions for some basins are based on a relatively small number of stream reaches (e.g., Shetucket, Piscataqua-Salmon Falls, and Middle Hudson each cover less than 100 km² in MA).

Figure 23: Distributions of thermal classes by stream order based on 30-yr (1971-2000) normal air temperature.

4.4 Climate Change Projections

In addition to predicting water temperatures and thermal classes based on historical air temperatures, the model was also used to make predictions under a series of climate change projections. These projections were generated using the predicted air temperature increases under the RCP8.5 emissions scenario over four 30-yr averaging periods centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, 2090 (see Section 2.4) (MA EEA, 2023). The projected summer air temperature increases were added to the PRISM 30-yr normal July air temperatures used in the historical predictions (Section 4.3) to calculate the expected July air temperature for each time horizon. In addition to using the median projected air temperature increases, water temperature projections were also generated using the 10th and 90th percentiles as provided by the climate dataset. Similar to the historical predictions, the projected mean July water temperatures were then used to classify each stream reach using the same thermal thresholds (Table 2).

Maps of the projected mean July water temperatures and thermal classes show large increases in water temperatures across the state as well as the conversion of many streams from Cold to Cool or Cool to Warm thermal classes as air temperature rises from the 2030 to 2090 averaging periods (Figure 24, Figure 25). All 16 basins in the state are projected to lose significant amounts, and in some cases all of, the reaches currently classified as Cold under the 30-yr (1971-2000) normal baseline (Figure 26). Statewide, the fraction of total river miles classified as Cold is projected to fall from 30% to 8.5% (72% reduction) by the 2090 averaging period under the median air temperature projections (Figure 27). Using the 90th percentile projections, that amount will fall even further to 5.5%, which is an overall reduction of 80% from the initial baseline.

Figure 24: Projected mean July water temperature under RCP 8.5 emissions scenario for 30-year averaging periods centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, 2090 using median air temperature projections.

Figure 25: Projected thermal classes under RCP 8.5 emissions scenario for 30-year averaging periods centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, 2090 using median air temperature projections.

Figure 26: Projected changes in thermal classes within each HUC8 basin under the RCP 8.5 emissions scenario for 30-year averaging periods centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, 2090 using median air temperature projections.

Note: each basin only includes flowlines within the MA state boundary and thus the distributions for some basins are based on a relatively small number of stream reaches (e.g., Shetucket, Piscataqua-Salmon Falls, and Middle Hudson each cover less than 100 km² in MA).

Figure 27: Projected changes in thermal classes across the state under the RCP 8.5 emissions scenario using the 10th percentile, median, and 90th percentile air temperature projections.

Lastly, the projected change in thermal classes can also be grouped by stream order (Figure 28). For first order streams, the fraction of total river miles classified as Cold would fall from 42 to 13% (69% reduction). For second order streams, that fraction would fall from 21 to 3.4% (84% reduction). For third, fourth, and fifth order streams, the classification (> 50% of river miles) would switch from Cool to Warm.

Figure 28: Projected changes in thermal classes by stream order under the RCP 8.5 emissions scenario using the median air temperature projections.

5 Discussion & Conclusions

A regional model was developed for predicting stream temperatures at gauged and ungauged streams and rivers based on air temperature and spatial landscape characteristics. The model was then used to create a series of projections of climate-driven changes in stream temperature and thermal habitat across the state of Massachusetts. The model was comprised of two components: 1) a non-linear regression model representing the functional relationship between air and water temperatures at a single location, and 2) a machine learning model (XGBoost) for estimating the parameters of the air-water temperature model spatially based on landscape characteristics. Together, these models demonstrated strong performance in predicting weekly water temperatures with an RMSE of 1.3 degC and Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) of 0.97 based on a 25% hold-out (i.e., validation) subset of the observed data. Although the regional model alone showed greater performance for the training dataset compared to the independent testing dataset, the performance of the two models combined was similar for predicting water temperatures between both dataset splits, which confirmed that the overall model does not suffer from overfitting. The performance of this model is similar to other regional stream temperature modeling studies (Kelleher et al., 2012; Mayer, 2012; Segura et al., 2015; Siegel et al., 2023); however, model performance metrics such as RMSE and NSE cannot be compared directly between different studies due to different timesteps (e.g., daily vs. weekly), spatial scales, and other factors.

After being fitted to the observed data, the models were used to predict mean July stream temperatures for each stream reach across the state (excluding large rivers with drainage areas > 10,000 km²) based on the 30-yr (1971-2000) normal mean air temperature to represent baseline conditions. Mean July water temperatures were also predicted for a series of climate change projections based on the RCP 8.5 emissions scenario over four 30-yr averaging periods centered on 2030, 2050, 2070, and 2090 (MA EEA, 2023). For both the baseline and climate change scenarios, the predicted stream temperatures were used to classify each reach based on thermal habitat thresholds for cold- and cool-water fish species (Beauchene et al., 2014). Lastly, the final dataset of predicted temperatures and thermal classes across the state were summarized with maps and figures showing changes in the distribution of thermal classes using the total river miles for each major drainage basin and stream order. Statewide, the model predicts a reduction in cold water habitat (mean July temperature < 18.45 degC) from 30% to 8.0% (a 73% reduction) by the 2090 averaging period based on median projections of air temperature increases. Furthermore, larger streams (orders 3 – 5) are projected to shift from predominately cool-water (18.45 – 22.30 degC) to the majority of river miles (> 50%) being warm-water habitat (> 22.30 degC).

The model was developed using the 1:100,000 scale (medium resolution) NHDPlusV2 hydrography dataset. Because of the importance of headwater streams in providing thermal habitat for critical life stages (e.g., spawning) of trout and other salmonids, a high-resolution (1:24,000) hydrography framework would be preferred. However, a review of available hydrography datasets showed that the high-resolution datasets (in particular NHDPlus High Resolution) are not yet suitable for regional modeling primarily due to network routing

inconsistencies and errors, which makes the calculation of basin-wide topographic and landscape variables challenging (Appendix B). The medium resolution NHDPlusV2 dataset was therefore used due to the availability of an enhanced routing network that was used to calculate a large number of climate, topographic, hydro-geologic, and landscape variables (Wieczorek et al., 2018). However, the model framework and methodology developed here can be readily extended to a high-resolution hydrography network once the routing issues addressed so that spatial attributes can be computed.

Another data limitation that affected this study was the lack of co-located flow and temperature monitoring data. Originally, the goal of this study was to develop a joint flow/temperature model that could assess the climate change impacts of both rising air temperatures and changing precipitation patterns. However, after compiling all known flow and continuous temperature datasets, only 30 stations were found across the state with more than 1 year of both flow and temperature data. In order to develop a model capable of generating reliable predictions for both gauged and ungauged streams, a larger number of stations are needed to ensure the diverse range of landscape and hydro-morphological conditions are represented. However, similar to the high-resolution hydrography issue, the model developed here can also be extended to incorporate flow data.

The U.S. Geological Survey is currently developing nationwide estimates of streamflow and temperature using a pair of process-based models (Precipitation Runoff Modeling System (PRMS) and SNTemp) (Markstrom et al., 2015; Sanders et al., 2017). When completed, the predictions from those models could be used as a basis for incorporating estimated flows at the 357 temperature stations used in this study. The availability of additional streamflow data is also anticipated through the USGS Flow Photo Explorer (FPE) project⁸, which is a database and machine learning platform for estimating streamflow in headwater streams using timelapse imagery.

The model developed for this project was designed to be easily adapted, extended and refined in future studies. In particular, this project will serve as the basis for a new regional stream temperature and flow modeling effort being led by Dr. Jennifer Fair of the U.S. Geological Survey. As part of that study, the current model will likely be extended to the full northeast U.S. region, for which existing input datasets (namely the enhanced routing network and associated drainage area attributes for NHDPlusV2) and observations (especially from the EcoSHEDS Northeast Stream Temperature Database and USGS NWIS) already exist. Furthermore, the addition of other spatial variables from the NHDPlusV2 attributes dataset can also be explored.

One other potential improvement would be to use an alternative model structure for the regional component instead of the boosted decision trees (XGBoost) of this methodology. Although the decision trees performed well in this study, using a spatially explicit model framework that is aware of the network structure may improve the ability of the model to represent the spatial autocorrelation of stream temperature (i.e., similarity in temperatures

⁸ <https://www.usgs.gov/apps/ecosheds/fpe/>

between connect reaches). Such frameworks include geospatial statistical models such as the Spatial Stream Networks model (SSN) (Isaak et al., 2017; Ver Hoef et al., 2019) and process-guided deep learning (PGDL) models built on a graph recurrent network (Jia et al., 2021).

The projected stream temperatures and thermal classifications generated by this project will be a valuable dataset for researchers and resource managers to assess potential climate change impacts on thermal habitats across the state. With this spatially continuous dataset, researchers and managers can identify specific reaches or basins projected to be the most resilient to climate change, and prioritize them for protection or restoration. As more datasets become available, in particular high-resolution hydrography with a consistent routing network and additional streamflow data at locations co-located with existing temperature sensors, this model can be readily extended and adapted to increase its spatial extent and resolution, and to incorporate flow data for assessing the impacts of not only rising air temperatures but also changing precipitation patterns.

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Appendix A

Technical Memorandum: Literature Review

Technical Memorandum

To: Rebecca Quiñones, MassWildlife
From: Jeff Walker, Walker Environmental Research LLC
Date: June 21, 2023
Project: DFW-2023-017 – Linking Water Temperatures and Flow Models in Massachusetts
Subject: Literature review of water temperature and flow modeling for identifying thermal refugia

This document provides a comprehensive literature review of stream temperature and flow modeling that was conducted as part of the project “Linking Water Temperatures and Flow Models in Massachusetts.” The primary goal of this project is to develop a joint flow and temperature model to identify thermal refugia for cold- and cool-water fish species across the state under current conditions as well as future climate change scenarios. The purpose of this review is to compile, summarize, and synthesize various models and methodologies that have been used for simulating stream temperature and/or identifying thermal refugia in gauged and ungauged river networks, and to provide recommendations for the model(s) to be developed under the next task of this project.

This review is comprised of the following three sections:

1. **Conceptual Model** presents a series of review papers and other literature that describe the processes and drivers of water temperature in streams and rivers, and the effects of climate change and various human activities.
2. **Modeling Methodologies** reviews a wide variety of statistical, mechanistic, machine learning, and hybrid models that have been used to predict stream temperatures.
3. **Conclusions and Recommendations** provides a synthesis of the previous sections and recommendations for potential modeling approaches that could be used for this project.

1 Conceptual Models

A number of review articles provide conceptual models of the physical processes and drivers governing water temperatures in streams and rivers. These conceptual models are useful for understanding what these processes and drivers are, and how their dynamics and relative importance vary over space and time.

Poole & Berman (2001) compare the relative influence of different stream characteristics on temperature across a range of stream sizes (Figure 1). For low-order headwater streams, they report that riparian shading and phreatic groundwater (referring to the deep aquifer as opposed to shallow, or hyporheic, groundwater) are the most important characteristics that provide stability of in-stream water temperatures. They also describe various external drivers such as topographic conditions, meteorological inputs, and hydrologic flows (i.e., advection) that affect

heat exchange fluxes within the stream. Internal processes are categorized as having either insulating effects by controlling the rate of heat exchange (e.g., channel width, riparian vegetation) or buffering effects that remove excess heat at high temperatures or gain heat when the stream is relatively cool (e.g., hyporheic groundwater flow). Lastly, they describe the various ways human activities can lead to thermal degradation including impoundments, water withdrawals, channel engineering, and changes to upland or riparian vegetation.

Stream Order	Stream characteristics				
	Riparian shade	Stream discharge	Tributaries	Phreatic groundwater	Hyporheic groundwater
1-2	High	Low	Moderate	High	Low-Mod
	Riparian shade and lateral phreatic groundwater inputs provide thermal stability. Lateral tributaries can frequently affect overall stream temperature. Large wood stores sediments and creates streambed complexity, driving hyporheic flow. (However, hyporheic influence is high and shade moderate in alpine meadow systems.)				
3-4	Moderate	Moderate	High	Moderate	Mod-High
	Temperature of lateral tributaries has strong influence on stream temperature. Effects of riparian shade modest. Thermal inertia due to larger flows becomes more important. Where floodplains form, channels patterns become more complex, and alluvial aquifers are well developed, hyporheic influence can be high. Large wood creates habitat complexity and forms channel-spanning jams that may provide significant shade to the stream.				
5+	Low	High	Low-Mod	Low-Mod	Mod-High
	Complex floodplain morphology creates a diversity of surface and subsurface flow pathways with differential downstream flow rates allowing for stratification, storage, insulation, and remixing of waters with differential temperatures. The resulting mosaic of surface and subsurface water temperatures continually remix to buffer channel temperature and create thermal diversity. The thermal inertia of large water volumes allows the stream to resist changes in temperature. Where side channels exist, shade from vegetation can be important.				

Figure 1: Relative influence of stream characteristics for varying stream sizes from Poole and Berman (2001)

Caissie (2006) describe another conceptual model focusing on the thermal processes governing temporal and spatial variability in stream temperatures. They group these processes into four categories: 1) atmospheric conditions, 2) topography, 3) stream discharge, and 4) streambed (Figure 2). In addition to narrative descriptions of the physical processes governing stream temperature, they also provide some conceptual plots showing the linear and non-linear relationships between water and air temperatures, as well as how the mean daily and diel variability of water temperatures changes from upstream to downstream along a river network (Figure 3). Next, they review different types of models for predicting water temperatures from one or more inputs. They describe three classes of models: regression, stochastic, and deterministic models and note that regression and stochastic models are most often applied at individual sites, while deterministic models are better suited to entire river networks. Lastly, they review various anthropogenic impacts on thermal regimes including deforestation, vegetation removal, and climate change, and describe how water temperatures relate to aquatic habitat and ecosystem functioning.

Figure 2: Conceptual models of thermal processes from Caissie (2006).

Figure 3: Water temperature relationships and variability from Caissie (2006).

More recently, Ouellet et al. (2020) provided a thorough review of all aspects of stream temperature research and application, going beyond just describing the physical processes and anthropogenic impacts by providing a number of recommendations for future work to improve our understanding and management of stream temperatures. Their review included descriptions of monitoring technologies and methodologies, thermal processes and fluxes, modeling approaches, and the real-world application of this research to support climate change adaptation and management (Figure 4). With the rising interest in thermal refugia for salmonids, they call for a better understanding of how vertical temperature variations within streams can be used as refugia as well as the structure, density, and connectedness of coldwater refugia patches at the landscape scale. They also provide a detailed summary of recent temperature modeling review articles and various statistical methods, which will serve as a useful reference for this project (Figure 10). They argue that deterministic models are most adequate for predicting the area and volume of thermal refuges due to their ability to perform multi-dimensional (2D or 3D) simulations, but that simpler statistical methods may also be useful for managers. Finally, they discuss how the lack of coordinated monitoring and modeling efforts makes it challenging to perform large-scale, regional assessments of the presence and climate change impacts on thermal regimes and refugia.

Fig. 4. Schematic of how thermal research, from data acquisition to modelling, supports climate change and management adaptation strategies to prevent the lost biological integrity due to thermal degradation. This also highlights the current pitfalls in data acquisition as well as the research gaps and highlights paths forward to better support management actions to address thermal degradation.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of temperature monitoring, modeling, research and management applications from Ouellet et al. (2020).

From an energy and water balance perspective, Leach et al. (2023) explain the thermal processes and fluxes that control stream temperatures from small streams to large rivers. These processes are grouped into three types of fluxes: 1) hydrologic advection, 2) stream-atmosphere energy exchange, and 3) energy exchange at the stream-bed interface (Figure 5). They also show how the relative importance (or magnitude) of the major fluxes varies with catchment area (Figure 5). Temperatures in small streams are governed largely by advection (inflows from upstream reaches, tributaries, and groundwater discharge), longwave radiation, and conductive heat flux between the water column and sediment bed. In large streams, shortwave solar radiation and sensible heat flux (transfer of heat based on air temperature) are primarily responsible for rising temperatures while larger latent heat fluxes release heat via evaporation.

Figure 5: Conceptual diagrams of thermal processes from Leach et al. (2023)

Lastly, Ficklin et al. (2023) provided a call-to-action commentary on the need for a more integrated approach to water temperature research due to the sensitivity and utility of water temperature as an indicator of climate change. They argue for more research on the interactions between climate, landscape, hydrology, and human activities on water temperature as the majority of research to date has focused primarily on “near-natural” streams. This has led to knowledge gaps in “*multiscale (temporal and spatial) patterns of change (notably at larger spatial and longer temporal scales); ‘interactions between human drivers’ (that is, global warming, landscape alteration and direct interventions); cumulative, cascading and ‘interconnected impacts’ across systems; and ‘uncertainties in making projections’ for locations (ungauged sites) and times (future projections) in rivers without river temperature observations.*” They also highlight the need for research on groundwater extractions, which may reduce groundwater discharge to surface waters and thus impact the occurrence and extent of cold-water refugia in headwater streams. Finally, they mention our EcoSHEDS stream temperature platform as a model of multi-agency data aggregation and for making temperature datasets more easily accessible.

1.1 Headwaters and Thermal Habitats

Low-order headwater streams are widely abundant, often accounting for more than half of the total river miles within a basin (Dodds & Oakes, 2008). They play important hydrologic and ecological roles by governing downstream water quality (Alexander et al., 2007; Dodds & Oakes, 2008) and for providing critical habitat for cold-water fish species such as brook trout and other salmonids (Kanno et al., 2015; Power et al., 1999). In temperate ecosystems, groundwater discharge can be a major component of headwater flows (Caissie, 2006; Leach et al., 2023; Poole & Berman, 2001). Because groundwaters are more stable throughout the year than surface waters, groundwater discharge provides a buffering effect resulting in relatively warm temperatures during winter and cool temperatures during summer (Caissie, 2006; Poole & Berman, 2001) (Figure 3). This buffering effect may also mean that cold water streams are less sensitive to air temperature than warmer streams (Luce et al., 2014). However, other climate

change phenomena, such as changes in precipitation patterns, may have other secondary effects on flow and vegetation that could in turn alter stream temperatures.

The availability of cooler summer temperatures provides critical thermal refugia for temperature-sensitive fish species (Power et al., 1999). Many headwater catchments are forested, which provides critical shading that keeps streams cool by limiting the incidence of shortwave solar radiation on the water surface (Garner et al., 2017; Johnson, 2004). Headwaters are also particularly vulnerable to climate change through increased droughts and rising air temperatures (Isaak et al., 2010). The importance of headwaters in providing cold-water habitat and thermal refugia coupled with their vulnerability to climate change has led to rising importance and urgency in identifying which specific headwaters will be most resilient to rising air temperatures and changing precipitation patterns.

Streamflow plays an important role in controlling temperature variations, especially in smaller headwater streams with relatively high advective heat fluxes (Leach et al., 2023) (Figure 5). One of the goals of this project is to develop a joint flow/temperature model able to capture those interactions so that the impacts of climate change on stream temperature and the availability of thermal refugia can be evaluated not only based on rising air temperatures, but also changes in the precipitation patterns.

Using a global dataset of flows and temperatures, Van Vliet et al. (2013) found that up to 26% of the increase in water temperatures in rivers having strong seasonal temperature and flow pattern (e.g., low flows and high temperatures in summer) could be indirectly attributed to declines in low flows driven by climate change. The lack of precipitation during droughts is expected to increase the importance of groundwater discharge in ensuring headwaters remain hydrologically connected and provide suitable cold-water habitat and thermal refugia for trout and other salmonids (Kaule & Gilfedder, 2021). And simulations using a mechanistic hydrologic model (Variable Infiltration Capacity, VIC) with down-scaled Global Climate Model (GCM) outputs showed substantial shifts in the timing and magnitude of both peak and low flows in the Midwest U.S. (Byun et al., 2019).

In the Northeast U.S., streamflow in most rivers is impacted to varying degrees by reservoir releases due to the large number of impoundments found in the region. The operations of these reservoir releases and dam operations can have significant effects on downstream thermal regimes (Daniels & Danner, 2020; Olden & Naiman, 2010; Seyedhashemi et al., 2021; Sinokrot & Gulliver, 2000). Furthermore, the location of reservoir outlets is important as surface releases tend to have higher temperatures due to warming of the reservoir epilimnion, while releases of deeper water tend to have lower temperatures due to stratification.

Climate change will have a variety of impacts on the health and functioning of aquatic ecosystems (Farr et al., 2021). Cold water fish species such as brook trout, brown trout and other salmonids are particularly vulnerable due to their reliance on headwater streams, which are sensitive to both rising air temperatures and changing precipitation patterns (Galbraith, 2013).

Dan Isaak and colleagues have conducted a number of studies on stream temperature dynamics and thermal habitat the Northwest U.S. For example, Isaak et al. (2010) used a spatial stream network (SSN) model to evaluate the effects of climate change and wildfire in central Idaho and found that warming air temperatures were already showing signs of affecting thermal habitat. Isaak et al. (2012) performed a statistical trend analysis of long-term stream temperature data for a collection of regulated and unregulated stations in the northwest U.S. and found widespread rising trends in water temperature across the region. Isaak et al. (2015) used the NorWeST data and SSN model to identify habitat refugia for two salmonid species in the Northern Rocky Mountains based on temperature predictions under moderate and extreme climate change scenarios.

Similarly, Mantua et al. (2010) combined a process-based hydrologic model (VIC) and a non-linear statistical stream temperature model to assess potential climate-driven changes in seasonal flows and water temperature, and the resulting impacts on salmonid populations across Washington state.

Thermal habitats are often defined based on one more temperature thresholds. For example, Beauchene et al. (2014) defined a set of temperature criteria for classifying streams as cold, cool, or warm in Connecticut (Figure 6).

Thermal Class	Water temperature (°C)		
	June–August mean	July mean	Maximum daily mean
Cold	<18.29	<18.45	<22.40
Cool	18.29–21.70	18.45–22.30	22.40–26.30
Warm	>21.70	>22.30	>26.30

Figure 6: Temperature metrics for classifying thermal classes in Connecticut from Beauchene et al. (2014)

2 Modeling Methodologies

2.1 Model Reviews

Over the past decade, there have been a few useful articles listing and comparing alternative stream temperature modeling approaches. These reviews provided a useful starting point for identifying potential methods that could be applied in this project. Of particular interest are any models used to generate predictions in ungauged streams (spatial extrapolation) and over large spatial (regional) areas.

Gallice et al. (2015) reviewed a large number of publications for predicting stream temperatures in ungauged basins (Figure 7). The most popular model type was multiple linear regression (MLR). One of interesting findings from this review is that in studies where multiple models were compared using the same dataset, the prediction accuracy tended to be relatively similar between those models suggesting the choice of model type was not as important as the gathering of observational or other input datasets. They also note the challenge of achieving a high level of accuracy with regional models, which they attribute in part to the challenge of acquiring local information about critical processes such as groundwater infiltration, water withdrawals, or degree of riparian shading. They discuss how few models predict temperatures over the full annual cycle, with most models focusing on only a particular season or portion of the year. Finally, they mention the issue of spatial averaging for predictor values, which can range from local scale (i.e., riparian land use along a single stream segment) to the full drainage area (i.e., land use composition across the entire area upstream of a reach).

Dugdale et al. (2017) provides an excellent review focusing specifically on deterministic (or process-based) models with the goals of 1) reviewing the foundations of temperature modeling, 2) comparing existing models based on how they represent energy flux processes, 3) describing differences in model implementations, features, and practicalities, and 4) discussing limitations and considerations for model use. Their review includes comparisons of large number of models (Figure 8) based on their features, spatial/temporal resolutions, and structures (Figure 9).

Finally, Ouellet et al. (2020) provided summaries of 1) previous review articles covering all types of temperature models, and 2) recent studies using a variety of different statistical models (Figure 10). They note that while deterministic (process-based) models are beneficial for estimating temperatures at various spatial scales, the high data requirements limits the ability to develop them for large, regional areas. In contrast, statistical models tend to have fewer data requirements and are more easily applied over large spatial scales. However, they can suffer from limited spatial and/or temporal transferability as they often do not include a physical representation of the underlying processes. They then discuss various studies that use statistical (e.g., multiple regression, GAMs, SSN) or machine learning (ANN) methods to predict temperatures over a range of scales.

Table 1. List of reviewed publications about statistical stream temperature prediction in ungauged basins.

Reference	Geographic location	Model type ^a	Number of sites	Number of years ^b	Temporal scale	Model precision ^{b,c}
Arscott et al. (2001)	Italy	MLR	22	1	Season	$R^2 = 0.37-0.8$
Bogan et al. (2003)	Eastern USA	AE	596	30	Week	$R^2 = 0.80, \sigma_e = 3.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Chang and Psaris (2013)	Western USA	MLR, GWR	74	n/a	Week, year	$R^2 = 0.52-0.62, \sigma_e = 2.0-2.3\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Daigle et al. (2010)	Western Canada	Various	16	0.5	Month	$\sigma_e = 0.9-2.8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
DeWeber and Wagner (2014)	Eastern USA	ANN	1080	31	Day	$\sigma_e = 1.8-1.9\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Ducharme (2008)	France	MLR	88	7	Month	$R^2 = 0.88-0.96, \sigma_e = 1.4-1.9$
Gardner and Sullivan (2004)	Eastern USA	NKM	72	1	Day	$\sigma_e = 1.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Garner et al. (2014)	UK	CA	88	18	Month	n/a
Hawkins et al. (1997)	Western USA	MLR	45	≥ 1	Year	$R^2 = 0.45-0.64$
Hill et al. (2013)	Conterminous USA	RF	~ 1000	1/site	Season, year	$\sigma_e = 1.1-2.0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Hrachowitz et al. (2010)	UK	MLR	25	1	Month, year	$R^2 = 0.50-0.84$
Imholt et al. (2013)	UK	MLR	23	2	Month	$R^2 = 0.63-0.87$
Isaak et al. (2010)	Western USA	MLR, NKM	518	14	Month, year	$R^2 = 0.50-0.61, \sigma_e = 2.5-2.8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Isaak and Hubert (2001)	Western USA	PA	26	1/site	Season	$R^2 = 0.82$
Johnson (1971)	New Zealand	ULR	6	1	Month	n/a
Johnson et al. (2014)	UK	NLR	36	1.5	Day	$R^2 = 0.67-0.90, \sigma_e = 1.0-2.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Jones et al. (2006)	Eastern USA	MLR	28	3	Year	$R^2 = 0.57-0.73$
Kelleher et al. (2012)	Eastern USA	MLR	47	2	Day, week	n/a
Macedo et al. (2013)	Brazil	LMM	12	1.5	Day	$R^2 = 0.86$
Mayer (2012)	Western USA	MLR	104	≥ 2	Week, month	$R^2 = 0.72, \sigma_e = 1.8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Miyake and Takeuchi (1951)	Japan	ULR	20	n/a	Month	n/a
Moore et al. (2013)	Western Canada	MLR	418	1/site	Year	$\sigma_e = 2.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Nelitz et al. (2007)	Western Canada	CRT	104	1/site	Year	n/a
Nelson and Palmer (2007)	Western USA	MLR	16	3	Season	$R^2 = 0.36-0.88$
Ozaki et al. (2003)	Japan	ULR	5	8	Day	n/a
Pratt and Chang (2012)	Western USA	MLR, GWR	51	1/site	Season	$R^2 = 0.48-0.78$
Risley et al. (2003)	Western USA	ANN	148	0.25	Hour, season	$\sigma_e = 1.6-1.8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Rivers-Moore et al. (2012)	South Africa	MLR	90	1/site	Month, year	$R^2 = 0.14-0.50$
Ruesch et al. (2012)	Western USA	NKM	165	15	Year	$R^2 = 0.84, \sigma_e = 1.5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Segura et al. (2014)	Conterminous USA	MLR	171	≥ 1.5	Week, month	$R^2 = 0.79$
Sponseller et al. (2001)	Eastern USA	MLR	9	1	Year	$R^2 = 0.81-0.93$
Scott et al. (2002)	Eastern USA	MLR	36	1/site	Season	$R^2 = 0.82$
Stefan and Preud'homme (1993)	Eastern USA	ULR	11	n/a	Day, week	$\sigma_e = 2.1-2.7\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Tague et al. (2007)	Western USA	MLR	43	4	Day	$R^2 = 0.49-0.65$
Wehrly et al. (2009)	Eastern USA	Various	1131	1/site	Month	$\sigma_e = 2.0-3.0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Westenbroek et al. (2010)	Eastern USA	ANN	254	1/site	Day	$R^2 = 0.70, \sigma_e = 1.8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
Young et al. (2005)	New Zealand	MLR	23	1	Season	$R^2 = 0.75-0.93$

^a AE: analytical expression; ANN: artificial neural network; CA: cluster analysis; CRT: classification and regression trees; GWR: geographically weighted regression; LMM: linear mixed model; MLR: multi-linear regression; NKM: networked kriging model; NLR: non-linear regression; PA: path analysis; RF: random forest; ULR: univariate linear regression.

^b n/a: not available.

^c σ_e : root-mean-square error; R^2 : coefficient of determination (sometimes referred to as the Nash–Sutcliffe index).

Figure 7: Reviewed modeling studies for predicting temperatures in ungauged basins from Gallice et al. (2015)

Table 1. List of reviewed process-based river temperature models (including programming language, source code and availability)

No.	Model name	Main reference(s)	Further reading	Language	Availability	Source code	URL for model download
1	BasinTemp	Allen (2008)	Allen et al. (2007)	N/a	Proprietary (Stillwater Sciences)		N/a
2	CE-QUAL-W2	Cole & Wells (2015)	Rounds (2007) Norton & Bradford (2009)	Fortran / Visual Basic	Free download	Yes	http://www.ce.pdx.edu/w2/
3	CEQUEAU	Morin & Paquet (2007)	Morin & Couillard (1990) St-Hilaire et al. (2000)	MATLAB / C++	Available on request	Yes	http://ete.inrs.ca/ete/publications/cequeau-hydrological-model
4	CrUSTe	LeBlanc et al. (1997)	LeBlanc & Brown (2000)	STELLA	N/a		N/a
5	Delft3D-FLOW	Deltares (2014)	Carrivick et al. (2012) Shen et al. (2014)	Fortran	Free download	Yes	http://oss.deltares.nl/web/delft3d/download
6	Heat Source	Boyd & Casper (2003)	Bond et al. (2015) Woltemade et al. (2016)	Python / Visual Basic	Free download	Yes	http://www.oregon.gov/deq/wq/tmdls/Pages/TMDLs-Tools.aspx
7	DHVS-M-RBM	Sun et al. (2015) Yearsley et al. (2001)	Yearsley et al. (2009) Yearsley et al. (2012)	Fortran	Free download	Yes	http://www.hydro.washington.edu/Lettenmaier/Models/RBM/index.shtml https://www.niwa.co.nz/freshwater-and-estuaries/our-services/catchment-modelling/water-allocation-impacts-on-river-attributes-waiora
8	GIS-STRTemp	Sansone (2001)	Sridhar et al. (2004)	N/a	N/a		http://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-ras/
9	HEC-RAS	Brunner (2016)	Drake et al. (2010)	Java	Free download		https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com/products/mike-11
10	MIKE 11	DHI (2016)	Loinaz et al. (2013)	N/a	Commercially available		https://www.mikepoweredbydhi.com/products/mike-11
11	MNSTREM	Sinokrot & Stefan (1993)	Sinokrot & Stefan (1994)	Fortran	Free download	Yes	N/a
12	Qual2K	Chapra et al. (2012)	Kannel et al. (2007)	Fortran / Visual Basic	Free download	Yes	http://www.ecy.wa.gov/programs/eap/models.html
13	RAFT	Pike et al. (2013)	Danner et al. (2012)	N/a	N/a		N/a
14	RMA11	King (2016)	Lowney (2000)	Fortran	Proprietary (Resource Modelling Associates)		http://ikingrma.iinet.net.au/
15	SHADE-HSPF	Becknell et al. (1997)	Chen et al. (1998a) Chen et al. (1998b) Bartholow (1984)	Fortran	Free download	Yes	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/hspf
16	SNTemp	Theurer et al. (1984)	Norton & Bradford (2009)	Basic, Fortran	Free download	Yes	https://www.fort.usgs.gov/products/sb/7557
17	Streamline	Rutherford et al. (1997)	Rutherford et al. (2004)	Fortran / Visual Basic	Available on request		N/a
18	TVA-RMS	Deas et al. (2003)	Null et al. (2010)	C	Available on request	Yes	N/a
19	WAIORA	Jowett et al. (2004)	Davies-Colley et al. (2009)	Delphi	Free download		https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/water-quality-analysis-simulation-program-wasp
20	WASP7	Wool et al. (2008)		Fortran	Free download	Yes	N/a
21	WET-Temp	Cox & Bolte (2007)	Watanabe et al. (2005)	C++	Available on request	Yes	N/a

Figure 8: List of process-based models reviewed by Dugdale et al. (2017)

Figure 9: Comparison of process-based models based on temporal and spatial resolutions from Dugdale et al. (2017)

Table 2 Recent reviews in water temperature modelling.		Table 3 Summary of the most recent statistical methods used to predict water temperature.						
Reference	Reviewed deterministic models	Reviewed statistical models	Study	Statistical methods	Scale	Covariate	Water temperature prediction	Region
Deas and Lowney, 2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-D (SNTMP, CQUAL, R1) 2-D (RMA, BETTER, CQUAL-K2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Linear and logistic Regression Stochastic (Box-Jenkins, Markov) 	Segura et al., 2015	multiple regressions	Watershed-regional	Range of covariates: micro-scale (e.g. riparian zone composition), meso-scale (watershed characteristics, e.g. drainage area), macro-scales (e.g. mean annual air temperature)	Monthly	USA
Calsic, 2006	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface energy fluxes; Inclusion of streambed fluxes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-D, 2-D SHARC CEQ/EAU SSTMP 	Isaak et al., 2014; Ashley Steel et al., 2016	Spatial stream-network models/wavelet analysis	Regional	Elevation, mean annual discharge, percent commercial area	Summer temperature using 13 different metrics (e.g. minimum, mean, or maximum temperature)	USA
Bengalaya et al., 2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SHARC CEQ/EAU SSTMP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regression Stochastic (Box-Jenkins, ARMA, PARMA) Non-parametric (K-nearest neighbours, Artificial Neural Networks) 	Isaak et al., 2017	Linear mixed model	Regional		August water temperatures	USA
Gallice et al., 2015	Stream shading models	Focus on ungauged basins:	Laanaya et al., 2017	Generalized Additive Models (GAM)	Regional	Air temperature and flow	Daily	Canada
Daggdale et al., 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Artificial Neural Networks Classification regression trees Geographically weighted regression Linear mixed model Network kriging model Nonlinear regression Path Analysis Random Forest 		Jackson et al., 2018	Generalized Additive Models (GAM)	River network - regional	Air temperature Range of landscape covariates such as: slope, elevation, channel orientation and riparian woodland	Daily	Scotland
			St-Hilaire et al., 2018	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) regression	Regional	Air temperature	Daily	Canada
			Boudreault et al., 2019	Functional regressions	Regional	Air temperature	Annual stream temperature curves	Canada
			Daigle et al., 2019	Gaussian function/stepwise regression	Regional	Large range of physioclimatic variables	Daily	Canada
			Zhu et al., 2019	Multilayer perceptron neural network models (MLPNN) Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS)	Watershed	Air temperature, discharge and Julian day	Daily	Croatia

Figure 10: Tables summarizing water temperature model reviews and statistical methods from Ouellet et al. (2020).

2.2 Regression Models

Linear and non-linear regression models are the most common type of model used for predicting stream temperature. This is likely due to their simplicity, ease of interpretation, and familiarity among researchers in general. Regression models have been used for a variety of goals including both inference (identifying which drivers, conditions, or processes are most important) and prediction (estimating temperatures through spatial and/or temporal extrapolation) (Shmueli, 2010).

Perhaps the most widely used regression model is a non-linear model for predicting weekly water temperature based on air temperature using an S-shaped logistic function (Mohseni et al., 1998). This approach is often implemented using two separate models to account for the seasonal hysteresis of temperature with one model representing the rising limb (spring warming) and the other the falling limb (fall cooling). Mohseni & Stefan (1999) further evaluated this approach by incorporating a physics-based heat budget model and found that linear extrapolations of water/air temp relationships are not valid due to the S-shaped relationship between air and water temperatures. These relationships are approximately linear between 0 and 20 deg C, but level off at high temperatures due to evaporative cooling. They conclude that linear models cannot be used to project high temperatures under climate change.

Morrill et al. (2005) compared multiple linear and non-linear air-water temperature models using weekly mean temperatures at 43 sites across the globe, and confirmed that the S-shaped logistic function used by Mohseni et al. (1998) performed best compared to other models for predicting water temperature based solely on air temperature.

Van Vliet et al. (2011) modified the original non-linear regression model from Mohseni et al. (1998) by adding a second independent term for streamflow. Adding flow to the model, which originally was only based on air temperature, improved the performance at 87% of 157 stations across the world. A sensitivity analysis then showed that air temperature increases of +2, +4, +6 degC would increase annual mean river temperatures by +1.3, +2.6, and +3.8 degC, respectively,

while reductions in flow of 20% and 40% would increase temperatures a further +0.3 and +0.8 degC, respectively. This is one of the first studies identified that evaluated the climate change effects of both rising air temperatures and changes in flow on water temperatures. The authors of this study later performed two follow-up studies using a mechanistic hydrology model (VIC) coupled with a 1D mechanistic stream temperature model (RBM) in large river basins worldwide and ultimately found that 26% of the increase in high water temperatures could be indirectly caused by changes in low flows (Van Vliet et al., 2012, 2013).

Piotrowski & Napiorkowski (2019) modified the non-linear regression model by Mohseni et al. (1998) with the goal of improving its performance for predicting daily temperatures by incorporating discharge and solar declination. They also provide a nice summary of other modifications to the original model. Using data from six different river basins in Europe and the U.S., they compared the performance of these different model alternatives along with an artificial neural network (ANN) and the semi-physical air2stream model described below. Overall, they found that the ANN model generally performed best at 4 of 6 streams, but also that their modified non-linear regression model outperformed the previous models, but not by much.

Kanno et al. (2014) also used the original nonlinear regression model from Mohseni et al. (1998), but used a Bayesian framework (JAGS) to better estimate parameter uncertainty. They collected fine-scale temperature data by deploying loggers at 36 locations within two stream networks in Connecticut during spring-to-fall 2010. They also evaluated various lagged-temperature metrics (0-4 hours, with the best fit being 3-hours) and split the data into warming and cooling periods to account for hysteresis. Using sub-daily (hourly) measurements, they showed that the shape of the water temperature vs lag-3 air temperature relationships were indicative of mainstem, warm water tributaries (relatively linear), cold water tributaries (more non-linear, S-shaped). These results showed that hourly temperature relationships could be used to identify which stations are most sensitive to the warmest air temperatures and may be indicative of groundwater influence or other controlling factors (shading). They concluded that fine-scale variations in stream temperature are not well captured by regional models, and that groundwater was a major driver of those variations.

Other studies have used the non-linear regression model of air vs water temperature from Mohseni et al. (1998) as a basis for understanding spatial variations in temperature dynamics. For example, Kelleher et al. (2012) estimated the primary drivers of thermal sensitivity using data from 57 stations in Pennsylvania. For each station, they fit a non-linear air-water temperature model and used the estimated slope of that model as a measure of thermal sensitivity (higher slopes indicated greater sensitivity). They then fit a multiple linear regression model to those estimated thermal sensitivities (slopes) using various site characteristics (e.g., channel size, solar radiation, stream order, baseflow index, elevation, etc). This analysis showed that in small streams, baseflow (BFI) was the major determinant of thermal sensitivity, while stream order was most important in larger streams. This confirms the general importance of groundwater discharge on temperatures in headwaters.

Segura et al. (2015) later used a similar methodology to understand the primary drivers of air-water temperature relationships using the USGS GAGES II database at 171 sites across the US. They first fit the nonlinear regression model by Mohseni et al. (1998) at each station, and then developed additional multiple linear regression models to predict the parameters (e.g., slope, intercept) of those models based on climatic, hydrologic and land cover attributes (Figure 11). They also evaluated the seasonal hysteresis of air-water temperature relationships and found drainage area was a major control on thermal sensitivity, while groundwater effects were most evident in spring and fall (although there were still significant in all seasons). The authors also noted that basin slope was negatively related to temperature due to shorter residence times in these reaches, giving water less time to warm from external inputs (air temperature, radiation).

Variable	Description	Extent	Unit												
DA	Watershed drainage area	Watershed	km ²												
P	Annual mean precipitation in the basin (1971–2000)	Watershed	cm												
T	Annual mean air temperature at the gauge locations (1971–2000)	Site	°C												
BF	Base flow index, ratio of base flow to total streamflow, expressed as a percentage and ranging from 0 to 100. Base flow is the sustained, slowly varying component of streamflow, usually attributed to groundwater discharge to a stream (Wolock, 2003)	Watershed	%												
DOF	Dunne overland flow, also known as saturation overland flow, is generated in a basin when the water table ‘outcrops’ on the land surface (because of the infiltration and redistribution of soil moisture within the basin), thereby producing temporary saturated areas. These saturated areas generate Dunne overland flow through exfiltration of shallow groundwater and by routing precipitation directly to the stream network. The data are estimated from a watershed simulation model – TOPMODEL (Wolock, 1993). The model was run throughout the conterminous USA	Watershed	%												
HOF	Horton overland flow, also known as infiltration excess overland flow, is generated in a basin when infiltration rates are exceeded by precipitation rates. The data are estimated from a watershed simulation model – TOPMODEL (Wolock, 1993). The model was run throughout the conterminous USA	Watershed	%												
TWI	Topographic wetness index, ln(a/S), where ‘ln’ is the natural log, ‘a’ is the upslope area per unit contour length and ‘S’ is the slope at that point. See http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2002JG002822 and Wolock and McCabe, 1995 for more details	Watershed	Ln (m)												
C	Subsurface flow contact time index. The subsurface contact time index estimates the number of days that infiltrated water resides in the saturated subsurface zone of the basin before discharging into the stream (Wolock et al., 1989; Wolock, 1997)	Watershed	Days												
Q	Estimated watershed annual runoff, mm/year, mean for the period 1971–2000 (King et al., 1989)	Watershed	mm/year												
U	Watershed percentage ‘developed’ (urban), 2006 (sum of low, medium and high intensity development and open space in the watershed (classes 21–24))	Watershed	%												
F	Watershed percentage ‘forest’, 2006 (sum of deciduous forest, evergreen forest and mixed forest (classes 41, 42 and 43))	Watershed	%												
U1	Maastem 100m buffer ‘developed’ (urban), 2006 (sum of low, medium and high intensity development and open space in the watershed (classes 21–24 in a buffer 100m each side of stream centerline))	RIPARIAN	%												
F1	Maastem 100m buffer ‘forest’, 2006 (sum of deciduous forest, evergreen forest and mixed forest (classes 41, 42 and 43 in a buffer 100m each side of stream centerline))	RIPARIAN	%												
H	Elevation at gauge locations	Site	m												
S	Mean watershed slope	Watershed	%												
AS	Mean watershed aspect, degrees (degrees of the compass, 0–360)	Watershed	°												
(A) Variables considered in predicting <i>m</i> and <i>b</i> of the LM															
Sample	LM variable	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i> ^{2a}	<i>DA</i> ^b	<i>P</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Q</i>	<i>BF</i>	<i>HOF</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>F1</i>	<i>U1</i>	<i>H</i> ^b	<i>S</i>
All sites	<i>m</i>	158	0.54	25.3	2.4			19.3				3.3			4.8
All sites	<i>b</i>	158	0.14	4.9					3.0			7.4			
<i>H</i> > 970 m	<i>b</i>	23	0.47				50.0								
200 m < <i>H</i> < 970 m	<i>b</i>	90	0.25	6.5					9.2	4.5	7.8				
<i>H</i> < 200 m	<i>b</i>	45	0.47	10.4		13.7			6.4			14.4	8.3		
(B) Variables considered in predicting seasonal thermal sensitivity (<i>m</i>)															
Spring	<i>m</i>	88	0.60	3.2				4.8							53.6
Summer	<i>m</i>	96	0.17	13.7			4.8								
Fall	<i>m</i>	92	0.45	17.1	4.1			21.5							4.4
(C) Variables considered on predicting mean stream temperature (<i>t_s</i>) for three seasons (variables with – where omitted in the models)															
Spring	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.92	2.0		73.6	1.3	1.2	–	–	–	0.2	–	0.5	13.1
Summer	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.89	7.2		22.3	1.3	3.9	–	–	0.6	–	–	0.6	53.6
Fall	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.85	2.2		77.6	0.7	–	–	–	–	0.5	–	–	4.7
Spring	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.73	0.8	0.7	–	–	11.2	43.2	–	–	–	–	–	17.6
Summer	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.82	5.9	–	–	–	3.4	16.0	–	–	–	–	–	3.6
Fall	<i>t_s</i>	180	0.63	0.9	1.4	–	–	5.3	18.0	–	–	–	–	–	38.3

Figure 11: Geospatial variables evaluated in multiple linear regressions from (Segura et al., 2015)

Hrachowitz et al. (2010) used multiple linear regression to identify the dominant controls on monthly maximum temperatures at 25 stations in Scotland. Summer temperatures were mainly driven by forest cover, which was assumed to be indicative of riparian shading, as well as catchment slope. They also coupled this multiple regression model with the non-linear air/water temperature model from Mohseni et al. (1998) to generate spatial predictions of maximum temperatures under a 100% forest scenario and two climate scenarios representing +2.5 and +4 degC increases in air temperature (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Estimated maximum weekly stream temperatures under present conditions, 100% forest scenario, and +4 degC climate scenario from Hrachowitz et al (2010)

2.3 Generalized Additive Models (GAMs)

Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) are an extension of generalized linear models that make no assumptions regarding the forms between the response and predictor variable(s). Instead of assuming a functional form (either linear or non-linear), GAMs models are constructed by summing a series of nonlinear functions (Wood, 2017).

Laanaya et al. (2017) compared traditional linear and nonlinear regression models (e.g., Mohseni et al., 1998) against a GAMs model for predicting water temperatures based on air temperature and flow at a monitoring station on the Sainte-Marguerite River in eastern Canada. The GAM model performed best (RMSE = 1.44 degC vs 1.83 to 2.56 degC for the other models) due to its greater flexibility in representing the non-linear relationships between water temperature and the two predictors. They also noted that the GAM model was more robust to “atypical data.”

Ouarda et al. (2022) developed a regional method for predicting daily temperatures at ungauged stations by using temperature duration curves (TDC) (analogous to flow duration curves for streamflow). The quantiles along the TDC were estimated by a GAM model in combination with spatial interpolation for transferring timeseries of daily percentiles. The model was applied to 126 stations in eastern Canada and found to be sensitive to the amount and quality of available data.

Siegel & Volk (2019) used both linear regression and GAMs models to generate spatiotemporal predictions of daily temperatures within four Columbia River tributary basins. By identifying and incorporating primary interactions between various climate and spatial variables, their objective was to generate reach-scale predictions in daily mean stream temperatures across each basin.

Models were fit using a set of time-varying (e.g., lagged air temperature) and spatial (e.g., elevation, drainage area) predictors (Figure 13). Separate models were fit during the spring warming and fall cooling periods to address hysteresis, although they note that the GAMs model could theoretically support hysteresis within a single model due to its greater flexibility. Interaction terms were also included between lagged air temperature and each of the other variables. The results showed that catchment area and elevation were the most common predictors among the spatial variables, while air temperature, snowpack, flow, and day of the year were most influential among the temporal variables. Baseflow index (BFI), lakes, slope and forest cover were only important locally in some areas. Overall, both linear models and GAMs models performed comparably (RMSE = approx. 1 degC); however, GAMs performed more poorly when less data were available. The data and code for this study are [available on Github](#).

Table 2 Table showing the variables considered for stream temperature models. Temporal (A) and spatial (B) variables considered as covariates in model selection with description of variable calculation, spatial and temporal characteristics, and rationale for inclusion.

Variable	Description	Spatial	Temporal	Rationale
A. Temporal variables				
D	Day of year (days)	NA	1 day means	Accounts for seasonal changes in length of days and solar angle
$T3_a$	Average air temperature from 3 day period before predicted day ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	From one point at headwaters	5 day means	The influence of air temperature on stream temperature accumulates over time
$T5_a$	Average air temperature from 5 day period before predicted day ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	From one point at headwaters	3 day means	The influence of air temperature on stream temperature accumulates over time
$T\Delta_a$	Difference between utilized averaged temperature variable ($T3_a/T5_a$) and mean temperature the day of predictions ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	From one point at headwaters	1 day means	Air temperature effects temperature in real time
S	Snowpack depth	From one point at headwaters	1 day means	More snowpack contributes colder water to streamflow
SAI	April 1st snowpack depth (cm)	From one point at headwaters	1 day means	Magnitude of late snowpack has prolonged effect on stream temperature into the summer (delayed discharge, riparian growth)
F	Flow at USGS gage (m ³ /s)	From one point near mouth	1 day means	Higher discharge creates more insulation against atmospheric influences. Seasonally different relationship (cooling in summer, warming in winter)
B. Spatial variables				
E	Average elevation of catchment area (m)	Summarized by catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Catchments with higher terrain will have cooler streams even if the site is at a lower elevation
$E\Delta$	Difference between E and the site specific elevation (m)	Summarized by catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Higher elevation sites experience cooler air temperatures and are closer to cooler headwaters
A	Catchment area of site (km ²)	Summarized by catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Sites further from headwaters have more time to be effected by atmospheric temperatures
BFI	Estimated Base flow index (mean low flow ÷ mean annual discharge)	Summarized by catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Areas with higher groundwater influence will have mitigated stream temperatures (lower highs and higher lows). Developed by Wolock (2003)
L	Percentage of catchment covered by lakes	Summarized by catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Lakes slow down water leading to increased atmospheric warming
SL	Slope of stream reach	Summarized by stream reach	NA	Steeper streams move cooler water downstream faster
FC/FR	Forest cover percentage of reach contributing area (FR) or catchment (FC)	Summarized by reach contributing area and catchment area of the stream reach	NA	Forested areas provide more stream shading and retention of moisture/snowpack

Figure 13: Temporal and spatial covariates used by Siegel and Volk (2019).

Just recently, Siegel et al. (2023) developed a regional GAMs model that accounts for both temporal and spatial covariates as well as their interactions. After fitting the model to data from the NorWeST database across the Pacific Northwest U.S., they generated daily temperature predictions for over 200k free-flowing reaches from 1990-2017 (Figure 14). Model performance was generally good with RMSE ranging from 0.85–1.54 degC across watersheds. Using monthly instead of daily temperatures reduced prediction error by 23%, on average. Spatial and temporal cross-validation showed that predictions were useful at ungauged reaches and over a wide range of landscape and climate conditions based on a Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The authors also noted that “accuracy of predictions was largely consistent across diverse climate years, demonstrating the ability of the models to capture the influences of interannual climatic variability and extend predictions to timeframes with limited temperature logger data.” Currently, only a preprint of this study is available with the final peer-reviewed publication expected to be accepted by PLOS One in the next couple weeks.

Fig 7. Stream temperature predictions averaged by season (top panel: summer; bottom panels: spring, fall, winter) to illustrate of the spatial extent over which predictions were made and temporal variability. Values were mapped to individual reach-contributing areas to improve visualization, but daily data are linked to each stream reach identifier in the National Hydrography Dataset version 2. Gray indicates reaches where we did not make predictions such as in reservoirs or because reaches were heavily influenced by dams (PDA > 0.25).

Figure 14: Seasonal stream temperature predictions using a GAM model from Siegel et al. (2023)

2.4 Signal Processing

Hare et al. (2021) used paired annual air-water temperature data to classify streams as having atmospheric, deep groundwater, shallow groundwater, or major dam signatures across the continental U.S. (CONUS). The classifications were based on a signal processing approach that estimated the amplitude ratio and phase lag of water and air temperature timeseries. They found that sites characterized as deep groundwater had far fewer increasing water temperature trends than stations with shallow groundwater or atmospheric signatures. The data and code for this project is [available on Zenodo](#). A web application called Paired Air and Stream Temperature Analysis (PASTA) was later released for using this methodology along with public temperature data and gridded climate observations (Daymet) to estimate groundwater influence on stream temperature (Hare et al., 2023).

Figure 15: Stream temperature trends and station categorization from Hare et al. (2021)

2.5 Bayesian Models

Linear and non-linear models for predicting daily stream temperatures have also been developed using Bayesian frameworks, which gained popularity in the 2010s for their ability to generate more robust estimates of model uncertainty.

Letcher et al. (2016) described six key issues regarding stream temperature modeling including:

1. Relationship between air and water temperature is non-linear (esp. at low and high temperatures)
2. Model accuracy can be improved by accounting for hysteresis
3. Water temperatures do not respond immediately to changes in air temperature due to thermal inertia
4. Continuous data are often sparse in many locations
5. Spatial and temporal autocorrelation can cause estimation problems
6. Beside air temperature, many other environmental parameters can affect water temperature

To address these issues, Letcher et al. (2016) developed a hierarchical linear autoregressive model, which was implemented using the JAGS Bayesian modeling framework. The model was fit to continuous temperature data collected at four sites in the West Brook watershed (central MA) from 1999 to 2013. A key feature of the model was the identification of the synchronization period for air and water temperatures (i.e., the timing of each year when the two temperatures are coupled).

Building off the work by Letcher et al. (2016), Hocking et al. (2018) developed a large regional stream temperature model using a Bayesian, hierarchical framework. This model is currently used by the EcoSHEDS project to estimate daily temperatures at a fine catchment scale across the northeast U.S. region ([model documentation available here](#)). In addition to air temperature, the EcoSHEDS model includes geospatial covariates for land cover, impounded area, and drainage area. The primary limitation of this model is that it is not aware of the river network, and therefore is limited in its ability to represent spatial autocorrelation (i.e., the fact that temperatures in one stream reach are relatively similar to the reaches directly upstream and downstream). Instead of using the river network, the model accounts for spatial autocorrelation by estimating random effect parameters at the site and HUC levels. This model is used to generate spatial predictions at all ungauged basins (excluding larger rivers with drainage areas > 200 km²). Predictions are also generated for a series of simple climate change scenarios including +2, +4, +6 degC air temperature increases.

Sohrabi et al. (2017) developed a piecewise Bayesian model for estimating daily mean stream temperatures that incorporates temporal autocorrelation, and the linear and non-linear relationships with air temperature and discharge. The model was fit using 34 stations in Boise River basin (Idaho). Discharge only had a significant effect on the model predictions in snow-dominated systems and was not important in rain-dominated or regulated (i.e., dammed) streams. An autocorrelation term prevented stream temperatures from changing to rapidly in response to changing air temperatures.

2.6 Geospatial Models

Gardner et al. (2003) used kriging to compare three distance metrics for representing spatial autocorrelation (Euclidian distance, network distance, and network weighted by stream order). The network weighted by stream order provided best spatial representation because it reduced the influence of tributaries on the main stem river.

Chang & Psaris (2013) showed that geographically weighted regression performed better than OLS regression at predicting spatial variations in thermal sensitivity and maximum temperature across 74 stations in Columbia River basin. GWR allows regression coefficients to vary spatially in order to represent spatial non-stationary processes. GWR results are not spatially autocorrelated (unlike OLS). Base flow index, contributing area and distance to coast were most important predictors for thermal sensitivity. Maximum temperatures were primarily controlled by baseflow index (BFI), forest cover, and stream order.

Jackson et al. (2017) used GAMs to predict min/mean/max temperatures based on landscape covariates (elevation, area, channel characteristics, etc.) at 25 sites in the UK. Their model also incorporated the spatial structure of the network using a river network smoother (RNS) (O'Donnell et al., 2014). Elevation, % riparian woodland, and catchment gradient were the best predictors of the minimum and mean temperature; while RNS and channel width were best for maximum temperature. The model was used to general spatial predictions of minimum, mean, and maximum temperatures across all reaches in the basin (Figure 16). Partial effects plots were also shown for each predictor to show spatially their relative importance.

Figure 16: Predicted maximum temperature, uncertainty, and partial effects of RNS and channel width from Jackson et al. (2017)

Jones et al. (2017) used a mixed effects generalized linear regression model from Jones et al. (2014) to predict seasonal temp under climate change scenarios across Crown of the Continent Ecosystem in the Northern Rocky Mountains. Model covariates included mean monthly air temperature (Daymet), topographic variables (elevation, slope, aspect), and the presence of lakes or glaciers. Separate seasonal models (spring, summer, fall) were developed for making monthly predictions within each season under baseline and RCP climate scenarios. The authors noted the challenge of predicting thermal variations in headwaters, or at fine-scale reaches due to the local effects of groundwater discharge, riparian shading and channel depth.

Figure 17: Predicted change in monthly temperatures under RCP4.5 from Jones et al. (2017)

Beaufort et al. (2022) used three statistical models to estimate the thermal peak – a metric representing summer thermal maxima – of each stream reach across France using a large

dataset from 1,700 stations. The thermal peak was defined as the interannual average of the mean temperature of the 30 hottest consecutive days of each year. Observed values were adjusted at incomplete stations to account for inter-annual climate variability by filling missing years of data at some stations using water/air temperature regression. They compared four models including multiple linear regression, artificial neural network (ANN), random forest (RF), and multi-model ensemble combining the first three models. Primary predictors included drainage area, air temperature, minimum monthly flow (similar to BFI), and vegetation cover. The RF model performed best (RMSE ~ 1.4 degC), but all three models performed similarly and yielded comparable spatial predictions. They also compared the results of the RF model to an SSN model for a smaller region and found SSN to be less biased, especially at high temperatures on major rivers and lowest temperatures on smaller streams. However, they concluded the additional effort of the SSN may not warrant its use for regional predictions. Lastly, they discussed the importance of regional models, which generally rely on statistical or machine learning models as being “most pertinent and parsimonious for management.” Spatial statistics models that incorporate network structure and covariance are likely most accurate, but require high data density, and thus they suggested using empirical regression or machine learning models instead.

Figure 18: Spatial predictions of thermal peaks using multiple modeling methods from Beaufort et al (2022).

2.7 Spatial-Stream Network (SSN) Models

Spatial-Stream Network (SSN) models are a special type of geospatial model that incorporate the spatial autocorrelation of stream temperatures using stream network distances (instead of Euclidian distances) through a spatial covariance structure (Peterson & Hoef, 2010; Ver Hoef et al., 2019). A central component of SSN models is the moving average functions that computes

both “tail-up” and “tail-down” correlations along a stream network. Data processing for SSN models is facilitated by the Spatial Tools for Analysis of River Systems (STARS) toolset for ArcGIS. The model can then be fitted using the SSN package for R.

The most widely used SSN model was developed as part of the NorWeST project for the Pacific Northwest U.S. by Dan Isaak and others (Isaak et al., 2017). The NorWeST SSN model predicts mean August stream temperatures across all perennial streams in the western U.S. under historical conditions and multiple climate change scenarios (Figure 19). The NorWeST SSN model has also been used, for example, to identify thermal refugia for salmonids (Isaak et al., 2010, 2015).

Figure 19: Predicted mean August stream temperature using SSN model from Isaak et al. (2017)

In addition to the Pacific Northwest, SSN models have also been used by the USEPA to create a regional stream temperature model for New England and another model for the Meduxnekeag River in Maine (Detenbeck et al., 2016; Figary et al., 2021). The New England SSN model was used to classify stream reaches by thermal regime (cold, cool, tidal, or warm) based on the medium resolution NHDPlusV2. Naomi Detenbeck (USEPA) is currently developing another SSN model for the Penobscot River basin in collaboration with the Maine Water Temperature Working Group (MEWTWG).

Figure 20: Predicted thermal regimes using SSN model of New England from Detenbeck et al. (2016)

A Bayesian version of the SSN model has also been developed to better estimate prediction uncertainty (Santos-Fernandez et al., 2022). However, this version of the SSN framework does not appear to be widely used and its current status is unknown.

Ruesch et al. (2012) also used the SSN framework to develop a spatially explicit statistical model of water temperature based on flow and spatial connectivity to estimate changes in cold-water habitat (Chinook salmon, rainbow trout, bull trout) due to climate change in the John Day River basin (Pacific Northwest). Solar radiation and interannual air temperature extremes were the primary drivers the spatial variability in extreme water temperatures from 1993 – 2009. The model predicts the maximum weekly mean stream temperature (MWMST) based on the log-transformed cumulative riparian solar exposure (CRSE) and maximum weekly maximum air temperature (MWMAT) based on data from 298 site-years (1993-2009) (Figure 21). The geostatistical component of the model was designed to represent the spatial configuration, longitudinal connectivity, and flow volume and direction of the network.

Figure 21: Predicted mean weekly stream temperatures in the Pacific Northwest from Ruesch et al (2012).

The primary limitations of SSN models are the data input requirements and need for a high density of observation data (Beaufort et al., 2022). SSN models also require networks to possess “simple” topologic characteristics, such as unidirectional flow, and do not support braiding or water diversions. As a consequence, SSN models are not readily applied to high-resolution hydrography datasets such as NHDPlus HR due to its well-known topological issues and inconsistencies. Most SSN models in the U.S. are based on the medium resolution NHDPlusV2 hydrography.

2.8 Semi-physical Statistical Models

One of the limitations of most statistical models is that they often do not directly incorporate or represent physical processes (e.g., energy transfer) or constraints (e.g., conservation of energy). However, there are few semi-physical statistical models that do attempt to incorporate physical processes within a statistical framework.

One relatively simple semi-physical statistical model is based on the concept of the equilibrium temperature, which is the water temperature at which the net heat flux at the water surface is zero (Edinger et al., 1968). The equilibrium temperature can be calculated using meteorological variables (solar radiation, air temperature, evaporation, etc). Using data from 596 USGS gages in the eastern and central U.S., Bogan et al. (2003) used regression models to show that weekly stream temperatures were linearly related to equilibrium temperature, and that this linearity was beneficial over the typical non-linear relationship water and air temperature. The slope and intercept of the linear relationship between water and equilibrium temperatures reflects the degree of shading and wind sheltering at each site. These parameters also indicate the relative influence of hydrologic fluxes and water use, which can be more important than surface heat exchanges at some locations.

Herb & Stefan (2011) modified the equilibrium temperature model for use in cold-water streams by incorporating stream bed heat flux due to groundwater discharge. This model

estimates daily temperatures based on climate conditions, shading, channel width, and groundwater discharge and temperature. This model was applied and validated at two reaches in a small watershed located in Minnesota.

Gallice et al. (2015) developed another “physics-derived statistical model” to predict monthly mean temperatures at ungauged reaches by incorporating physical processes using an analytical solution to the energy balance equation over an entire stream network. This physics-inspired model was compared to a multiple linear regression model, both of which were based on air temperature, radiation, riparian forest cover, channel slope, stream orientation, shading, network characteristics, and drainage area. Ultimately, the regression model performed slightly better; however, its parameters were not physically constrained and thus gave counter-intuitive results for some stations.

Lastly, air2stream is another semi-physical statistical model that incorporates a process-based heat budget and requires only air temperature and discharge as input variables (Toffolon & Piccolroaz, 2015). The code for this model is [available on Github](#). The air2stream model includes 8 parameters, which are estimated using a Monte Carlo-based optimization procedure. While this model achieved very strong performance at three stations in Switzerland, it is not clear how it could be extrapolated to ungauged basins. Piccolroaz et al. (2016) later compared alternative formulations of the air2stream model against regression-based and stochastic models.

2.9 Process-Based Models

Process-based models (also known as deterministic or mechanistic models) are an important class of models for simulating water temperature dynamics (Dugdale et al., 2017). These models typically perform numerical simulations of water and energy (heat) budgets incorporating various mechanisms affecting water temperatures. Because these models incorporate the physical processes of energy transfers, they are often well suited for understanding temperature dynamics as well as for performing scenario analyses such as land use changes or climate change impacts. However, most process-based models have substantial data requirements and often contain a large number of unknown parameters that must be calibrated.

A large number of process-based modeling studies were reviewed for this project; however, the vast majority were defined on smaller spatial scales. Only a few instances were found where a deterministic model was used across multiple basins at the regional scale. This was not unexpected due to the data requirements and effort needed to calibrate these models.

Li et al. (2015) developed a large-scale temperature model for the continental U.S. (CONUS) using the Community Earth System Model (CESM) coupled with the Model for Scale Adaptive River Transport (MOSART). Because it was developed at the continental scale, it used a coarse spatial resolution incorporating only major rivers of the U.S. The model was used to evaluate the changes in water temperature due to both climate change and reservoir operations.

Figure 22: Predicted seasonal stream temperatures across CONUS using a large-scale earth system model from Li et al (2015)

The only other known instance of a process-based model being developed over a large spatial scale is an on-going effort by the USGS to create stream temperature predictions for all reaches across the country using the Precipitation-Runoff Modeling System (PRMS) (Markstrom et al., 2015) coupled with a process-based temperature model (Sanders et al., 2017) based on SNTemp, which was originally developed by Theurer et al. (1984). PRMSE is a hydrologic model that has been used to predict streamflow at large spatial scales including the CONUS (Regan et al., 2018). By combining PRMS and SNTemp, this system can generate couple flow and temperature predictions. The development of these models is using the National Hydrologic Model geofabric, which contains approx. 50k reaches at a coarse spatial scale. Predictions from this model study are expected in the next year or two.

Note that a coupled PRMS/SNTEMP model was also used to support the development of a process-guided deep learning (PGDL) model for the Delaware River basin (Jia et al., 2021), as described in the PGDL section below.

2.10 Machine Learning Models

Advances in computer hardware and software have led to a new class of data-driven models built generally referred to as Machine Learning (ML), which are gaining interest in the water resources community (Appling et al., 2022).

For example, Varadharajan et al. (2022) discusses many of the potential benefits and important considerations of using ML to better understand and manage river water quality. Zhu & Piotrowski (2020) reviewed a large number of studies using ANN and other ML methods that focus on forecasting water temperatures. And Feigl et al. (2021) compared the performance of six models including linear regression, random forest, XGBoost, feed-forward neural networks (FNNs) and two kinds of recurrent neural networks (RNNs). All six models were applied to 10

catchments in Austria, and found to perform similarly (median RMSE difference between models was 0.08 degC). The ML models were also compared to a linear regression model and the semi-physical statistical model air2stream, both of which had higher average RMSEs by approx. 1.0 and 0.5 degC, respectively, compared to the ML models.

Deep learning (DL) models are a special type of ANN that contain multiple hidden neural network layers. Due to their ability to handle large quantities of complex and diverse data, DL models provide new opportunities for creating hydrologic models that address many of the common challenges associated with other types of models (Shen, 2018; Shen et al., 2018, 2021).

ML models, especially deep learning models that involve multi-layered neural networks, are often considered “black boxes” limiting their utility in understand the primary controlling factors (i.e., variable importance). However, there are some methods such as eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) that have been used to understand how these models work and how they learn underlying relationships between variables similar to the variable importance analysis used in traditional statistical models (Topp et al., 2023).

One of the benefits of deep learning models is data synergy. Fang et al. (2022) demonstrate that deep learning models for predicting soil moisture and streamflow benefited from data synergy by using all available data spanning multiple, heterogenous regions. Deep learning models built using pooled data outperformed region-specific models that were each fit to data from a single region, thus invalidating the assumption that these models perform best when the data represent a relatively homogenous spatial area.

2.10.1 Classic Machine Learning

So-called “classic” machine learning models include a variety of algorithms that can be used for either supervised or unsupervised learning. Popular examples include tree-based models such as random forests and gradient boosted trees (XGBoost), k-nearest neighbors, and support vector machines (SVM).

For example, Hill et al. (2013) used random forests to assess the impact of human alterations based on comparisons of mean summer, winter, and annual temperatures relative to a set of reference stations with minimal disturbance using hundreds of stations across the CONUS. For each temperature metric, they evaluated the relative influence of each predictor variable using ranked importance (% increase in mean squared error). The top three most important predictors for mean summer temperatures were air temperature followed by watershed area and BFI.

More recently, Weierbach et al. (2022) compared a few different ML models including SVM and XGBoost to predict monthly water temperatures at 78 locations in the Mid-Atlantic and Pacific Northwest U.S. The models were used to generate temporal predictions at individual sites as well as spatio-temporal predictions across all reaches within each basin. The ensemble XGBoost performed best performance for the ungauged basin predictions with a median RMSE of 0.62

degC. ML methods significantly also outperformed multiple linear regression models. Air temperature, month, and solar radiation were the primary controlling factors and streamflow was only significant at 10 of the sites.

Souaissi et al. (2023) compared a series of non-parametric (MARS), semi-parametric (GAMs) and machine learning (random forests, XGBoost) models for regional estimation of maximum water temperatures at ungauged locations. The best performance resulted from the GAMs and MARS models possibly due to their flexibility and ability in reproducing thermal extremes.

Lastly, Wade et al. (2023) used conditional inference random forests to evaluate the relative importance of different controls on stream temperature at 410 stations across the CONUS. The RF models were trained to predict maximum monthly stream temperature and thermal sensitivity (slope of air-water temperature relationship). Variable importance rankings were then evaluated to determine which controls (climate, human impacts, watershed characteristics and hydrology) were the most influential predictors. Their results showed both regional and seasonal variations in variable importance and highlighted the lack of a universal set of drivers across all stations.

2.10.2 Artificial Neural Networks

A number of water temperature models used artificial neural networks (ANNs). One limitation of ANN models is the high uncertainty when extrapolated (Chenard & Caissie, 2008). Some suggest excluding predictions for reaches outside the range of training data. For example, Rocchini et al. (2011) proposed the concept of a 'map of ignorance,' which was used by DeWeber & Wagner (2014) as described below.

Chenard & Caissie (2008) developed one of the first ANN models for predicting daily water temperatures in a small watershed in New Brunswick (52 km² drainage area). Multiple models were developed for both the daily mean and maximum water temperature using air temperature, water level, and day of year as predictors. Models were only developed for a single monitoring station. Model performance was assessed using the RMSE and bias of each year (1992-2002).

DeWeber & Wagner (2014) used an ANN ensemble model to predict daily temperatures for all stream reaches within the Eastern Brook Trout Joint Venture (EBTJV) region, which spans from Maine to southern end of the Appalachian Mountains (Figure 23). They evaluated four alternative models with the final model including air temperature, landform (drainage area, aspect as measure of solar exposure, and baseflow index), and forest cover. Sensitivity analysis identified air temperature, 7-day lag air temperature, and drainage area as the most important predictors. Forest cover was less important and had a positive effect from 0 to 70% cover, which was unexpected and may be caused by correlations with other land use or watershed (e.g., drainage area) metrics, followed by a negative effect up to 100%. The model was fit to 886 sites (RMSE=1.91 degC) over 1980–2009 and validated at 96 sites (RMSE=1.82 degC) as well as using one year (2010, which was relatively warm) of data (RMSE=1.93 degC). Daily predictions were aggregated to mean July temperatures over 1980-2010. They trained 100 ANNs using different

starting weights to create an ensemble, then used the ensemble median for the final predictions as this was more robust than using a single ANN. The model was primarily used for 1) inference by evaluating the relationships between water temperature and each covariate, and 2) spatial prediction by estimating mean summer temperatures in all stream reaches across the region (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Predicted mean July temperature during 1980-2010 in the EBTJV region from DeWeber and Wagner (2014).

Piotrowski et al. (2015) compared different ANN architectures (multi-layer perceptron, product-units, adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference systems and wavelet neural networks) as well as a k-nearest neighbor approach to predicting stream temperatures based on air temperature, discharge and solar declination for two rivers in Poland. They found that the simplest ANN architecture (multi-layer perceptron) performed best, and that all ANN architectures performed much better than k-nearest neighbors.

Piotrowski et al. (2021) compared two ANN models (perceptron, product unit network) against an extended logistic regression (NLogR3 from Piotrowski & Napiorkowski (2019)) and the semi-deterministic model (air2stream) for predicting changes in daily water temperatures due to climate change in the US and Poland. The models were driven by air temperature and model-generated (GR4J) streamflow estimates. They found differences of more than 2 degC in the predicted temperatures, depending on which temperature model was used, and advocated for the use of multiple models when assessing climate impacts.

Liu et al. (2018) compared a linear regression model against an ANN model for predicting changes in stream temperature due to climate change and water diversions in the Eel River

basin (CA). Inputs to the model included air temperature and predicted runoff and baseflow using a VIC hydrologic model. The models were fitted to data collected at two stations. The fitted models were then used to generate predictions using downscaled climate change forecasts for RCP4.5 and 8.5. They found that climate change may increase water temperatures by 1.2 – 2.4 degC while diversions could cause further increases of 1.0 degC.

2.10.3 Long Short Term Memory (LSTM)

Long short term memory (LSTM) networks are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN), which unlike other ANNs possess memory cells that can maintain state of a system across timesteps. In effect, the memory cells give LSTM models the ability to simulate temporal autocorrelation, which is commonly found in many environmental timeseries, especially temperature.

Rahmani, Lawson, et al. (2021) developed a daily mean temperature model using an LSTM model trained on 118 basins across the US ([data and code](#)). They found that adding streamflow as an input improved model performance, even when the streamflow was estimated using a pre-trained LSTM model instead of direct observations. They also note some of the complex ways streamflow and temperature can be related. The models were trained using basin-average climate forcing and attributes from the GAGES-II dataset and observed temperatures at USGS gages. Rahmani, Shen, et al. (2021) developed another LSTM model designed specifically for generating predictions in data-scarce, un-monitored and dammed basins ([data and code](#)) and found that LSTMs can perform well in spatial extrapolation, but are sensitive to major impoundment releases as are most temperature models.

Qiu et al. (2021) developed an LSTM model for the Yangtze River to assess the impact of the Three Gorges Reservoir. The LSTM model outperformed companion models including air2stream, random forests and back propagation neural network.

Lastly, Sadler et al. (2022) recently developed a multi-task deep learning (DL) model to simultaneously predict both streamflow and temperature. They hypothesized that by training a DL model to predict multiple variables, the model will be able to better learn the underlying hydrologic processes as compared to a single-task DL model that predicts only one of the two variables. The model consisted of an LSTM layer and two parallel, densely connected output layers (one for flow and one for temperature), and was trained using 101 USGS stations across the U.S. using the CAMELS dataset. The results mixed with the multi-task model performing better than a single-task model in some cases, but not others. For example, the multi-task model was better at predicting spring temperatures due to higher flows, but was poorer in summer. This was potentially due to the seasonal patterns of streamflow and temperature with snowmelt dominating flows during the spring, and baseflow in summer. Ultimately, the authors concluded that multi-task DL models should be used with care as it can perform significantly worse in some areas, and even in places where it can work well, it needs to be properly fine-tuned. The code and data for this model are available on ScienceBase (Sadler et al., 2021).

LSTM models have been also been used for rainfall/runoff predictions. Kratzert et al. (2018) showed that LSTM models can outperform catchment as well as distributed (regional) process-

based models for predicting flows in ungauged basins ([code available on Github](#)). Feng et al. (2020) developed a LSTM model for predicting streamflow using data integration techniques ([code available on Github](#)).

2.10.4 Process-Guided Deep Learning

Given the rapid developments in Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and models, there is growing interest in integrating these modern ML methods into process-based models for simulating physical systems such as streams and rivers. Willard et al. (2022) provides a review of the different techniques used to create these so-called hybrid models.

Process-guided deep learning (PGDL) models are one relatively new class of models that use process-guided models to constrain deep learning models so that they can directly learn the physics-based processes and constraints of a system. Three common elements of a PGDL model are: 1) use of an LSTM architecture to support temporal autocorrelation, 2) pre-training the deep learning model using output from a process-based model and then using observation data to fine-tune that model, and 3) incorporation of physics-based constraints (such as conservation of mass or energy) into the loss function used to train the deep learning model.

PGDL models have been developed for predicting lake temperatures (Read et al., 2019), stream temperatures (Jia et al., 2021), and streamflow (Shen et al., 2022). One of the major limitations of the PGDL approach is that it requires development of both a process-based model and a deep learning model, which is challenging at large scales due to the data requirements and level of effort needed. Consequently, there are relatively few applications of a PGDL model to make predictions at ungauged basins or across large spatial areas. As Read et al. (2019) notes: “Despite the compelling results from early PGDL efforts, applications to Earth-science modeling will likely be limited until PGDL can be shown to provide reliable generalizability to multiple systems and extrapolation beyond the original training data set.” Nonetheless, it is worth considering PGDL modeling approaches as the pace of advancements in this area is rapidly increasing thanks to general improvements in deep learning algorithms, as well as the development of new large-scale datasets such as the PRMS/SNTemp predictions for CONUS being developed by USGS.

Read et al. (2019) developed a PGDL model for predicting lake temperatures in Minnesota and Wisconsin. Compared to a traditional deep learning model (LSTM) and a process-based model (General Lake Model, GLM), the PGDL model performed best with the lowest RMSE at most lakes (0.5 degC lower) (Figure 24). The PGDL model was based on an LSTM architecture that was pre-trained using an uncalibrated process-model with a loss function that incorporated the conservation of energy.

Figure 24: Distribution of test RMSE at 68 lakes using process-based, deep learning, and PGDL models from Read et al. (2019)

Jia, Zwart, et al. (2021) developed a PGDL model for predicting streamflow and temperature in the Delaware River Basin using a recurrent graph network model. This graph network structure allowed the model to explicitly capture spatial autocorrelation between river segments, while LSTM cells captured the temporal autocorrelation. This model was pre-trained using output from the process-based PRMS/SNTemp model, and then fine-tuned using observation data. It outperformed both a processed-based model. The final model outperformed the PRMS/SNTemp model itself by 2.2 degC (RMSE) as well as traditional ANN and RNN models by 0.1 degC (RMSE) when using all available training data. An experiment in which the observation data for one river segment was excluded from the training dataset showed the PGDL model was slightly better than the RNN model (0.1 to 1.2 degC RMSE varying by segment), though not compared to any of the other models.

Building off the work by Jia, Zwart, et al. (2021), Zwart et al. (2023) developed a set of PGDL models for generating near-term forecasts of river temperatures at five specific locations in the Delaware River basin. Separate models were developed for each station. The models were pre-trained using output from the process-based PRMS/SNTemp model, along with simulated release temperatures from two major upstream reservoirs generated using the General Lake Model (GLM). They also used data assimilation to improve model forecast predictions by adjusting LSTM states using recent water temperature observations. Forecast predictions are made at 72 stations, including both gauged and ungauged. The datasets and source code for this study are all available on ScienceBase (Oliver et al., 2021; Zwart, Oliver, & Watkins, 2022; Zwart, Oliver, Watkins, et al., 2022). The live forecasts are [available for viewing online](#).

Jia et al. (2022) also developed a different PGDL model using a state-aware graph (SAG) for evaluating the impacts of reservoir releases on stream temperature. This model used simulation-based embedding (SE) in order to transfer information from reservoirs where release data was available to those where it was not using a pseudo-prospective (PP) approach.

Chen et al. (2022) presented a novel meta learning approach for predicting stream temperature and flow in river networks using the Delaware River Basin as an example. By using meta learning, this new method allows the model to learn different parameters for different sets of stream segments. As a result, the model can learn better even when data are sparse at some locations. Similarly, Jia, Lin, et al. (2021a) evaluated the use of adaptive learning to inform spatial and temporal sampling strategies that would optimize DL model training.

Lastly, Topp et al. (2023) compared two PGDL models based on a recurrent graph convolution network (RGCN) and a temporal convolution graph model (Graph WaveNet) in the Delaware River basin. They found that while both models performed similarly, the Graph WaveNet model outperformed RGCN in 4 out of 5 experiments designed to test the models' ability to generate predictions under conditions not included in the training dataset. They also used Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to show that the Graph WaveNet was able to better learn the physical processes that govern the observed spatial variability in temperatures.

3 Conclusions and Recommendations

The ultimate goal of this project is to develop a model for identifying cold- and cool-water thermal refugia under current and future climate change conditions across the state of Massachusetts. To achieve this, such a model will need to have the following two properties:

- Provide continuous spatiotemporal predictions of temperatures for both gauged and ungauged stream reaches (ideally at a high spatial resolution)
- Incorporate both air temperature and flow data as the primary covariates for generating predictions under future climate change scenarios that reflect both rising air temperatures and changing precipitation (and thus flow) patterns.

Based on this literature review, I identified the following model frameworks and methodologies that could meet these requirements:

- Non-linear Regression of Air/Water Temperature Relationship coupled with Multiple Linear Regression of Spatial Characteristics (Kelleher et al., 2012; Segura et al., 2015)
- Generalized Mixed Effects Regression Model (Jones et al., 2014, 2017)
- Spatial GAMs Model (Siegel et al., 2023)
- Random Forest (Beaufort et al., 2022; Wade et al., 2023)
- Spatial Stream Network (SSN) Model (Detenbeck et al., 2016; Isaak et al., 2017)
- Artificial Neural Network (ANN) (DeWeber & Wagner, 2014)
- LSTM Deep Learning Model (Rahmani, Lawson, et al., 2021; Rahmani, Shen, et al., 2021)
- Process Guided Deep Learning (Jia, Zwart, et al, 2021; Topp et al., 2023)

In the next task of this project, these alternatives will be reviewed and compared in more detail in order to select a final modeling approach. It is worth noting that many of the studies reviewed above found relatively similar performance when multiple models were compared using the same input and observational datasets. This suggests that there is no one model

framework that would necessarily perform significantly better than any other, and that with the right datasets any of these available options may yield sufficiently accurate results (Gallice et al., 2015).

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Appendix B

Technical Memorandum: Dataset Compilation and Review

Technical Memorandum

To: Rebecca Quiñones, MassWildlife
From: Jeff Walker, Walker Environmental Research LLC
Date: May 15, 2023
Project: DFW-2023-017 – Linking Water Temperatures and Flow Models in Massachusetts
Subject: Water temperature and streamflow monitoring datasets, hydrography and landscape characteristics, and climate change projections to support linked temperature and flow modeling in Massachusetts

This technical memorandum summarizes a series of datasets that I have obtained and reviewed in support of the upcoming linked temperature and flow modeling in Massachusetts. In this memo, I first describe and summarize all available streamflow and water temperature monitoring data across the state that I obtained from a variety of sources. I then identify and review all stations with paired flow and temperature data. Next, I compare alternative hydrography datasets and associated landscape characteristics for potential use in the linked flow and temperature model. Lastly, I summarize available datasets for representing climate change projections of future streamflow, air temperature, and precipitation. The compilation of these datasets was completed under Task 1 - Data Gathering of the Scope of Work for DFW-2023-017 – Linking Water Temperatures and Flow Models. This memo serves as the final deliverable for this task and denotes its completion.

Flow and Temperature Monitoring Datasets

Continuous streamflow and water temperature datasets were obtained from various sources including online databases and direct communications with individual monitoring organizations (Table 1). These datasets were combined into a single, uniform database using the R statistical programming language.

I first obtained continuous temperature data from the EcoSHEDS northeast stream temperature database and both temperature and flow data from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) National Water Information System (NWIS). I also retrieved both flow and temperature data for one station (HOPB) in the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), and at multiple stations from the Plum Island Ecosystems Long-term Ecological Research (LTER) Network and Harvard Forest with assistance from Jennifer Fair (USGS).

I also downloaded temperature data from the National Water Quality Monitoring Council (NWQMC) Water Quality Portal (WQP)¹, but discovered that it only included discrete measurements (i.e., probe measurements collected as part of weekly or monthly sampling programs). Because there were no continuous datasets from the WQP, it was excluded from

¹ <https://www.waterqualitydata.us/>

further review as future modeling efforts will likely require continuous temperature monitoring data.

I also requested both flow and temperature data from watershed organizations across the state through an email sent via the Massachusetts Rivers Alliance on February 9, 2023 with the assistance of Sarah Bower. In response to this request, I received continuous data from Charles River Watershed Association (CRWA), Hoosatic River Watershed Association (HOORWA), and the Ipswich River Watershed Association (IRWA). I also received responses from other watershed organizations referring me to the EcoSHEDS stream temperature database where their data were already stored.

All together, these various data sources included 181 flow stations and 1,206 temperature stations (Table 1). Maps showing the locations of these stations indicate that both flow and streamflow stations are relatively well distributed across the state with the exception of Martha's Vineyard and Nantucket where no known stations exist (Figure 1). Flow stations tended to have much longer periods of record than temperature stations as shown in the cumulative distributions for the number of years of data at each station (Figure 2). For example, the median periods of record were only 1 year among all temperature stations compared to 20 years among the flow stations. Similarly, 80% of the temperature stations had 4 years or less of data compared to only 26% of the flow stations. These summaries only include data collected between 1994, which is the year with the earliest available temperature measurement across all datasets, and 2022, which is the most recent full calendar year. Note that some flow stations include significantly longer periods of record, going back to the start of the 20th century in some cases.

Table 1: Flow and temperature data sources

Name	Description	Source	# Flow Stations	# Temp. Stations
CRWA	Charles River Watershed Assoc.	Pers. Comm. (Lisa Kumpf, 2/13/2023)	0	6
EcoSHEDS	EcoSHEDS Northeast Stream Temperature Database	http://db.ecosheds.org	0	1,107
HOORWA	Hoosatic River Watershed Assoc.	https://hoorwa.org/monitoring	0	18
HRF	Harvard Forest	https://harvardforest1.fas.harvard.edu/exist/apps/datasets/showData.html?id=HF070	4	4
IRWA	Ipswich River Watershed Assoc.	Pers. Comm. (Ryan O'Donnell, 3/3/2023)	0	19
NEON	National Ecological Observatory Network	https://data.neonscience.org/data-products/DP1.20053.001 , https://data.neonscience.org/data-products/DP4.00130.001	1	1
USGS-NWIS	U.S. Geological Survey National Water Information System	https://waterdata.usgs.gov/nwis	172	45
PIE-LTER	Plum Island Ecosystems (PIE) Long-term Ecological Research (LTER) Network	https://pie-lter.ecosystems.mbl.edu/welcome-plum-island-ecosystems-lter	4	6
TOTAL			181	1,206

Figure 1: Continuous streamflow and temperature stations by data source, 1994 – 2022.

Figure 2: Cumulative distribution of number of years of data for streamflow and temperature stations, 1994 – 2022.

Stations with Paired Flow and Temperature Data

The flow and temperature stations were spatially merged to identify the temperature station nearest to each flow station. For each nearest neighbor pair of flow/temperature stations, the daily flow and temperature data were then merged to determine the amount of paired flow and temperature data at those stations. Station pairs with less than 100 days of overlapping flow and temperature data were excluded to focus on station pairs with at least one season of overlapping data. The cumulative distribution of the distance between each pair of flow/temperature stations shows that 65% ($n = 40$) of the 62 station pairs were within 100 m and 71% ($n = 44$) were within 1 km of each other (Figure 3). For the 40 station pairs within 100 m of each other, the cumulative distribution of the # years of overlapping data showed that half of those stations had at least 8 years of data, with the maximum overlapping period being 21 years (Figure 4).

A map of the 40 paired stations located within 100 m of each other shows that most of these station pairs are located in the northern half of the state (Figure 5). These paired stations include 1 pair from NEON, 4 from Harvard Forest (HRF), 4 from Plum Island Estuary LTER (PIE-LTER), and the remaining 31 from USGS. Of the USGS stations, 21 had both flow and temperature data collected by USGS, and the remaining 10 stations had flow data from USGS and temperature data from EcoSHEDS².

Timeseries of the daily flow and temperature data for the 40 paired stations co-located within 100 m of each other are provided in Attachment A.

² The latter set of stations indicates situations where a non-USGS organization deployed a temperature logger nearby an existing USGS gage.

Figure 3: Cumulative distribution of paired flow and temperature station distances. Only includes station pairs with at least 100 days of overlapping data.

Figure 4: Cumulative distribution of # years of overlapping data for each paired flow and temperature station. Only includes station pairs with at least 100 days of overlapping data and located within 100 m of each other.

Figure 5: Map of paired flow and temperature stations within 100 m of each other and with at least 100 days of overlapping data

Hydrography and Landscape Characteristics

Table 1 lists a series of hydrography datasets that I obtained and compared for potential use as the basis for the linked flow and temperature modeling. The following descriptions of those datasets are grouped by resolution beginning with the two medium resolution delineations, and followed by the remaining four high resolution delineations.

Medium Resolution Delineations

Two hydrography datasets (Hydro100k and NHDPlusV2) were based on medium resolution delineations. The flowlines for these delineations are relatively similar in most cases except that the Hydro100k dataset does not distinguish between waterbody boundaries (shorelines) and stream reaches (flowlines). Therefore, the NHDPlusV2 dataset would be preferred as the flowlines reflect the routing network. NHDPlusV2 also includes a companion dataset called “Select Attributes for NHDPlus Version 2.1 Reach Catchments and Modified Network Routed Upstream Watersheds for the Conterminous United States”³ that contains hydro-geological and landscape metrics for each stream reach based on a modified version of the NHDPlusV2 routing network. This dataset includes many potentially useful metrics for supporting the linked flow and temperature modeling such as land cover composition, base flow index, estimated groundwater recharge rates, water table elevation relative to land surface, topographic wetness index, and bedrock permeability, among others.

³ <https://dx.doi.org/10.5066/F7765D7V>

Table 2: Hydrography datasets

Dataset	Description	Source	Resolution	Landscape Characteristics?
SHEDS NECD	SHEDS Northeast Catchment Delineation	https://ecosheds.github.io/necd	High	Y
NHDPlusHR	NHD Plus High Resolution	https://www.usgs.gov/national-hydrography/nhdplus-high-resolution	High	N
NHDPlusV2	NHD Plus V2, Medium Resolution	https://nhdplus.com/NHDPlus/NHDPlusV2_home.php	Medium	Y
hydro25k	MassDEP 1:25,000 Hydrography	https://www.mass.gov/info-details/massgis-data-massdep-hydrography-125000	High	N
hydro100k	MassGIS 1:100,000 Hydrography	https://www.mass.gov/info-details/massgis-data-hydrography-1100000	Medium	N
SARIS	MassWildlife	Pers. Comm. (Jason Stolarski, 4/28/2023)	High	N

Figure 6: Medium resolution hydrography datasets (NHDPlusV2, hydro100k).

High Resolution Delineations

Four of the hydrography datasets (SHEDS NECD, NHDPlusHR, hydro25k, and SARIS) are based on high resolution delineations. The SHEDS NECD flowlines are nearly identical to those in the NHDPlusHR (Figure 7). The MassDEP 1:25,000 hydrography (hydro25k) and the SARIS (MassWildlife) hydrography datasets are also similar to those in NHDPlusHR, but each included additional detail in select watersheds (Figure 8, Figure 9).

Only the SHEDS NECD hydrography dataset includes an existing companion dataset with landscape and basin characteristics, which was developed to provide the covariates for the SHEDS northeast stream temperature model⁴. Landscape characteristics are not available for the NHDPlusHR dataset due to widespread routing issues, which make it challenging to compute upstream basin characteristics at a regional scale. Addressing these routing issues is a labor intensive task that would be beyond the scope of this project, at last on a state-wide scale. Unfortunately, the SHEDS hydrography dataset uses an alternative reach identification system, which is not easily transferred to NHDPlusHR (i.e., there is no cross-walk table between the two) and therefore the SHEDS landscape metrics cannot be easily applied to the NHDPlusHR hydrography layers.

For the MassDEP and SARIS hydrography datasets, I inquired about existing landscape characteristics datasets from Brad Compton of UMass Amherst (pers. comm. 3/16/2023). He

⁴ <https://ecosheds.org/models/stream-temperature/latest>

referred me to the MA Conservation Assessment and Prioritization System (CAPS) dataset⁵, which was developed to support their Index of Ecological Integrity (IEI) projects. However, he cautioned that the CAPS dataset is raster-based (including hydrography), and therefore would be of limited value for modeling using vector-based hydrography as will be necessary in this project. Therefore, there does not appear to be any existing landscape datasets associated with the MassDEP or SARIS hydrography datasets.

Figure 7: Comparison of NHDPlusHR and SHEDS NECD high resolution flowlines.

⁵ <http://umasscaps.org/>

Figure 8: Comparison of NHDPlusHR and MassDEP 1:25,000 Hydrography (hydro25k) high resolution flowlines.

Figure 9: Comparison of NHDPlusHR and SARIS (MassWildlife) high resolution flowlines.

Climate Change Projections

I identified two datasets for representing projected changes in flow, air temperature, and precipitation under future climate change scenarios.

Streamflow Projections

The U.S. Forest Service Office of Sustainability and Climate and Rocky Mountain Research Station generated a dataset⁶ of projected streamflow metrics using the Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) model coupled with downscaled temperature and precipitation climate change projections (Figure 10). Projected streamflow metrics include mean annual and seasonal streamflow, flood metrics (1.5, 10, and 25 year), frequency statistics (7Q1, 7Q10), baseflow index (BSI), and center of flow mass (CFM). The projections were generated using downscaled CMIP forecasts under the RCP8.5 emissions scenario and for three time periods: historical (1977-2006), mid-century (2030-2059), and end-of-century (2070-2099). The dataset is based on the NHDPlusV2 Medium Resolution hydrography dataset, and can be downloaded as a File GeoDatabase containing the historical and projected values as well as the absolute and relative changes for each stream reach.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the US Forest Service Streamflow in a Changing Climate website.

Air Temperature and Precipitation Projections

The Resilient MA Climate Change Clearinghouse for the Commonwealth⁷ provides projected seasonal and annual changes in air temperature and precipitation (Figure 11). These projections were generated for the RCP 8.5 emissions scenario using downscaled Global Climate Models (GCMs) and a stochastic weather generator. Projections are provided for 4 target decades (2030, 2050, 2070, 2090) based on annual and seasonal periods (Figure 12). Temperature metrics

⁶ <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/6a6be7d624db41638a24b659305af522>

⁷ <https://resilientma.mass.gov/home.html>

reflect min/mean/max temperature, exceedance frequencies, degree days, heatwaves, and heat stress. Precipitation metrics include total and daily maximum precipitation, exceedance frequencies, and the number of consecutive dry or wet days. Projections are provided for each HUC8 basin across the state. The dataset is available as a USGS data release⁸.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the Resilient MA interactive map showing the projected maximum summer temperature for the 2050 target decade.

Selected layer: Maximum Temperature

Watershed (HUC 8): Middle Connecticut

Season	Baseline	2030	2050	2070	2090
ANNUAL	82.8	3.6 (2.7-5.4)	6.3 (4.5-8.1)	9.0 (6.3-11.7)	10.8 (7.2-13.5)
SPRING	79.0	3.6 (1.8-5.4)	5.4 (3.6-8.1)	8.1 (5.4-10.8)	9.9 (6.3-13.5)
SUMMER	82.8	3.6 (2.7-4.5)	6.3 (3.6-8.1)	9.0 (5.4-11.7)	10.8 (7.2-13.5)
FALL	79.1	3.6 (2.7-5.4)	6.3 (4.5-7.2)	9.0 (6.3-10.8)	10.8 (8.1-13.5)
WINTER	70.0	4.5 (2.7-6.3)	6.3 (4.5-9.0)	9.0 (6.3-12.6)	10.8 (8.1-14.4)

Table shows the median (50th percentile) value by future target decade and season as compared to baseline values. Lower and upper bounds (the 10th-90th percentile range) is presented in parenthesis. Projected decreases are denoted by a minus (-) sign. The value highlighted in dark green is the value corresponding to the season and decade currently selected within the legend controls. Values are presented as absolute change.

Figure 12: Screenshot of table from Resilient MA interactive map showing the projected maximum temperature for the Middle Connecticut HUC8 basin across varying seasons and target decades.

⁸ <https://www.sciencebase.gov/catalog/item/62e948a0d34e749ac04cc084>

Attachment A: Timeseries of Paired Flow and Temperature Data

Description: The following figures shows timeseries of paired daily mean streamflow and water temperature data at flow and temperature stations located within 100 m of each other and with at least 100 days of overlapping data.

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104430
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104430
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: PIE-LTER:Forest-CartCreek
Temp. Station: PIE-LTER:Forest-CartCreek
POR: 2001-06-21 to 2021-12-17

Flow Station: PIE-LTER:Urban-SawMillBrk
Temp. Station: PIE-LTER:Urban-SawMillBrk
POR: 2001-06-22 to 2021-12-17

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104455
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104455
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104475
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104475
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01095220
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01095220
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01095375
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01095375
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104460
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104460
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: HRF:BU
Temp. Station: HRF:BU
POR: 2007-12-21 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01170100
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01170100
POR: 2015-10-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01095503
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01095503
POR: 2015-03-19 to 2022-07-27

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01168250
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01168250
POR: 2015-07-23 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01101500
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:bosds3 [10365]
POR: 2015-07-09 to 2021-05-12

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104453
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104453
POR: 2007-10-01 to 2015-10-06

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01100627
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:balimp [10347]
POR: 2015-07-07 to 2021-10-05

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01173000
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01173000
POR: 2018-10-09 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104405
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104405
POR: 2011-11-15 to 2015-10-08

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01104410
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01104410
POR: 2011-11-16 to 2015-10-05

Flow Station: PIE-LTER:Swamp-CedarSwamp
Temp. Station: PIE-LTER:Swamp-CedarSwamp
POR: 2005-10-12 to 2009-09-28

Flow Station: NEON:HOPB
Temp. Station: NEON:HOPB
POR: 2019-05-01 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01171100
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:West Brook_West Brook 0 (Master) 01171100
POR: 2020-02-01 to 2021-11-07

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01108000
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01108000
POR: 2019-09-12 to 2020-10-05

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01108410
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01108410
POR: 2019-09-12 to 2020-10-05

Flow Station: PIE-LTER:Upperlps
Temp. Station: PIE-LTER:Upperlps
POR: 2001-06-27 to 2001-12-18

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01100568
Temp. Station: USGS-NWIS:01100568
POR: 2022-08-03 to 2022-12-31

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01331500
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:Above Chutes [9107]
POR: 1999-05-10 to 1999-09-28

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01103455
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:W0408 [7077]
POR: 2007-06-28 to 2007-10-24

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01105638
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:W2034 [6740]
POR: 2009-06-05 to 2009-10-01

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01197500
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:W1100 [7117]
POR: 2007-06-25 to 2007-10-18

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:011058837
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:W1909 [6756]
POR: 2009-06-18 to 2009-10-06

Flow Station: USGS-NWIS:01105880
Temp. Station: EcoSHEDS:W2080 [6768]
POR: 2009-06-19 to 2009-10-01

